

EXPLORING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTION AND LEARNER EMPOWERMENT AMONG THE FACULTY OF KCAST BOARD PROGRAMS: A CONVERGENT PARALLEL STUDY

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Exploring the Relationship Between Differentiated Instruction and Learner Empowerment among the Faculty of KCAST Board Programs: A Convergent Parallel Study

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Abstract

The study aimed to explore and describe the lived experiences and strategies of the board program instructors, particularly those instructors under the Institute of Teacher Education, Criminology Program, and Agriculture Program with regards to the implementation of differentiated instruction and learner empowerment in the students' learning process. This study employed the mixed method design, utilizing parallel convergent approach. The participants of the study were the instructors under the KCAST Board Programs. There were 75 instructors who were randomly selected for quantitative data and 14 for the qualitative: which were purposively selected. In the quantitative phase, the results revealed that the instructors who has been implementing differentiated instruction and learner empowerment was very high. Also, both variables have positive moderate correlation. In qualitative phase, it was revealed that their lived experiences and strategies were impacted by the different factors; recognition and accommodation of students, diversity to enhance teaching pedagogy, equity and inclusion in education, effective time management in education, collaborative learning for inclusive engagement, and harmonizing academic standards and students' diverse needs. Additionally, the instructors' insights with regards to the implementation of differentiated instruction and learner empowerment were fostering academic success through personalized learning and differentiated instruction, cultivation of optimal learning environment for student success, effective teaching practices for student engagement, collaborative professional growth for effective teaching, and lifelong learning and professional growth in education. In addition, the quantitative data mostly corroborated with the qualitative data.

Keywords: *differentiated instruction, learner empowerment, mixed methods study, KCAST board program instructors, Philippines*

Introduction

Learner empowerment is a process where students gain the authority and skills to take control of their own learning journey. It involves students prioritizing meaningfulness, competence, impact and choice in their education. As a crucial prelude to affective, cognitive and behavioral learning, learner empowerment is a crucial component of any effective educational process as it is characterized by students feeling capable, finding the assignments for the course important, and believing they have an influence on the learning process. Although the aim of learner empowerment is to provide students with increased control and independence in their education, there is a possibility that certain educators may hesitate to let go of their customary power. This situation may result in a power conflict as student's sense their increased authority is not completely endorsed or acknowledged by the faculty (Li, 2023).

There is a crucial issue with learner empowerment with English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners in China. The effectiveness and influence of learner empowerment among EFL Learners initiatives on educational outcomes in China are becoming increasingly important. Understanding how empowering learners through personalized, inclusive, and technology-enhanced approaches contributes to academic performance, self-efficacy, and general well-being is becoming increasingly important. In line with this necessity, some earlier studies have evaluated the influence of learner-related factors on learner empowerment. Despite technological and pedagogical advances, a large percentage of learners continue to experience barriers that limit their capacity to take control of their learning path. Access to specific educational resources, restricted possibilities for self-directed investigation, and insufficient support structures for developing choice and initiative are characteristics of these difficulties. Additionally, factors influencing learner empowerment challenges faced in implementing empowerment strategies, and the measurable outcomes associated with fostering empowered learners in Chinese EFL learners. Moreover, the lack of a comprehensive understanding of these factors hinders the development of effective educational strategies and interventions aimed at promoting learner empowerment across diverse educational settings (Chu, 2023).

In similar vein, a study conducted at the Senior High School Department of Eastern Samar State University, Philippines aimed to determine if student empowerment is present among the subjects and whether it affects their academic performances. The study found that the absence of learner empowerment not only impedes individual academic achievement but also hinders the development of critical thinking, problem-solving, and self-efficacy skills, and that a lack of student engagement in learning is often a reaction to a lack of empowerment, as when students are denied formal power in the classroom, they frequently disengage from learning, which has a negative impact on their academic performance and can lead to academic failure (Pomentil, 2023).

The social value of this study, exploring the relationship between learner empowerment and differentiated instruction, has major implications for teachers in higher education. This research will lead to a better understanding of how differentiated instruction empowers students and how teaching strategies can affect learners' interest and engagement. By examining the relationship between these two variables, the study will result in improved teaching strategies and better-equipped teachers who can effectively empower

their students. Moreover, the relationship between differentiated instruction and learner empowerment is addressing urgent problems in the realm of education, and a thorough investigation of this relationship will address critical challenges in the educational landscape, such as the need for more effective instructional practices that cater to diverse learner needs and promote student empowerment. This research is crucial in impacting overall educational quality and developing student empowerment, as well as enhancing teaching strategies, and its importance extends beyond the realm of education, as it directly contributes to the improvement of educational pedagogy. In a broader societal context, the results of this study emphasize the importance of employing effective instructional practices that empower learners in order to satisfy the growing demands for an educated and well-equipped society.

The relationship between differentiated instruction and learner empowerment has been explored in various studies, including the study of Frymier, (2009) work, "The Role of Students Characteristics and Teachers Behavior in Students' Learner Empowerment," and study of Yil, (2020) entitled, "Perceived Academic Motivation and Learner Empowerment Levels of EFL Students in Turkish Context." Both studies emphasized the significance of teacher-student relationships, teaching effectiveness, and student motivation, which can be effectively enhanced through differentiated instruction. Despite extensive research, most studies focused on broader educational settings, leaving a gap in understanding the specific challenges faced by educators. Notably, there is a lack of studies investigating the relationship between differentiated instruction and learner empowerment among faculty in specific programs like teacher education, criminology, and agriculture at KCAST, particularly in Baranggay Maniki, Kapalong, Davao del Norte, using mixed method approach. This gap emphasizes the needs for comprehensive studies employing both qualitative and quantitative techniques to better understand how differentiated instruction influences learner empowerment in these fields.

The researcher intends to disseminate the findings of this research through hardbound copies distributed strategically within our academic community and by publishing in a certain international journal, ensuring it reaches a global audience. Coordinating with the research office to arrange a formal presentation and distribute hardbound copies to faculty and staff during the event, fostering direct engagement and discussions and ensuring that hardbound copies are prominently available in the library, making them easily accessible to students and researchers.

Research Questions

This study employed a convergent parallel mixed method approach to investigate the relationship between differentiated instruction and learner empowerment among faculty members of KCAST board programs, including instructors from teacher education, criminology, and agriculture, in order to gather quantitative and qualitative data concurrently, merge findings, and utilize them to address the research problem, resulting in a more comprehensive understanding through combined analysis. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of differentiated instruction and learner empowerment of the faculty of KCAST board programs?
2. What is the relationship of differentiated instruction and learner empowerment among the faculty of KCAST board programs?
3. What are the experiences and strategies of the board program instructors in implementing differentiated instruction and fostering learner empowerment?
4. What are the insights of the board program instructors with regards in implementing differentiated instruction and learner empowerment?
5. To what degree do the quantitative data corroborate with the qualitative data?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a mixed methods design, which involves the combination of quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis in a single study. Therefore, integrating the two forms of data provide a more comprehensive understanding of complex research problems than using quantitative or qualitative methods alone. Hence, it can provide greater generalizability, contextualization, and credibility of research findings. Moreover, mixed methods research plays a vital and multifaceted role in research, extending far beyond mere validation. By seamlessly integrating quantitative and qualitative methods, this approach enables a comprehensive and holistic perspective on the subject of study, enhancing understanding, exploring complexity, strengthening rigor and credibility, and fostering interdisciplinary collaboration (George, 2021).

In the context, the researcher utilized a mixed-methods approach, specifically a convergent parallel design, to examine the relationship between differentiated instruction and learner empowerment. The researcher believed that through employing this approach, the researcher was able to collect and analyze quantitative and qualitative data concurrently, with the aim of obtaining a more comprehensive and robust understanding of the relationship between the two variables. Additionally, by adopting a mixed-methods approach, the researcher was able to gain a more holistic and nuanced understanding of the complex interplay between differentiated instruction and learner empowerment.

The research design selected for this study was a convergent parallel mixed method. In this approach, the quantitative and qualitative components are given equal priority, and the findings from each strand are compared, contrasted, and integrated to identify areas of convergence, divergence, and complementarity, allowing the researcher to triangulate the data and develop a richer, more nuanced

perspective on the phenomenon under study. The key benefit of the convergent parallel design is its ability to leverage the strengths of both quantitative and qualitative methods, leading to a more complete and robust understanding of complex, multifaceted research topics (Tomasi et al., 2018).

Within the given context, the convergent parallel design allowed the researcher to gather data from multiple sources, including surveys and interviews to gain insights into the experiences and perceptions of faculty of KCAST board programs. The quantitative data, such as survey responses, provided measurable indicators of the relationship between differentiated instruction and learner empowerment, while the qualitative data, such as interview transcripts, offered a deeper understanding of the contextual factors and individual experiences that shaped the relationship of both variables.

Consequently, this research utilized a descriptive-correlation approach. Descriptive correlational research is a quantitative method that aims to describe the relationship between two or more variables without manipulating them. Moreover, descriptive correlational research cannot establish causality, as there may be common-causal variables that produce the observed relationship. However, it is valuable for identifying patterns and trends, generating hypotheses, and providing a foundation for further analytical research. Additionally, descriptive correlational research is a non-experimental design that describes the characteristics of variables and the relationships between them, without manipulating the variables (Stangor & Walinga, 2014).

Within the appropriate perspective, the researcher utilized descriptive-correlational approach in quantitative phase of this study to clearly defining the variables and using validated measurement instruments to assess the levels of the indicators for each variable. This approach allowed the researcher to conduct thorough reliability and validity assessments to ensure the data is of high quality as well as providing detailed descriptive statistics to give readers a comprehensive understanding of the distribution and characteristics of the data. Thus, the researcher carefully analyzed the strength and statistical significance of the correlations between the two variables, differentiated instruction and learner empowerment. This provides insights into the nature and magnitude of the relationships of the two variables which can inform the interpretation and implications of the findings.

On the other hand, the qualitative phase of this study employed phenomenological inquiry to further develop the qualitative frame. Phenomenological inquiry is a qualitative research approach that seeks to deeply understand and describe the universal essence or meaning of a particular phenomenon as directly experienced by individuals. Moreover, phenomenological inquiry employs methods like in-depth interviews and personal narratives to gather rich, detailed descriptions, with the goal of uncovering the common features and meanings that characterize the experience across multiple people, rather than seeking broad generalizations. This idiographic approach provides unique insights into the lived realities and subjective understandings of a phenomenon that cannot be accessed through quantitative means alone (Öhlén & Friberg, 2023).

In context, the researcher utilized this approach in qualitative phase of this study to explore and understand the perspective of the faculty of KCAST board programs in implementing differentiated instruction and learner empowerment this includes their lived experiences, struggles, coping mechanism, and insights. By focusing on the first-hand perspectives of participants and bracketing the researcher's own preconceptions, phenomenology provides a nuanced and empathetic understanding of the participant of this study. This approach allows the researcher to facilitate and explore personal growth through reflection, and contributes to rich theory development. Thus, thoroughly analyzing the data of the participant using phenomenological inquiry allowed the researcher to enhance comprehensive grasp of the complexities of the human experience that cannot be fully accessed through quantitative methods alone.

Participants

The study focused on the instructors from the teacher education, criminology, and agriculture programs of KCAST. These departments are part of the college's board programs at KCAST which is the focus of this study. The faculty members were selected both quantitative respondents as well as qualitative participants. This selection allows the researcher to comprehensively explore the relationship between differentiated instruction and learner empowerment, drawing on insights from varied academic disciplines to better understand how instructional strategies can be tailored to enhance student engagement and success.

Quantitative Phase

The respondents of this study were the faculty members of the teacher education, criminology, and agriculture programs of Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology (KCAST) during the second semester of the 2023-2024 academic year. These faculty members were chosen as the respondents because the study aimed to examine the relationship between differentiated instruction and learner empowerment among the faculty of KCAST's board programs. Since the study focused on instructors in these specific programs, it was appropriate to include faculty members from teacher education, criminology, and agriculture who had been working at the institution for 2-3 years or more, while faculty members with less than 2 years of experience at KCAST were not included as respondents.

Further, the respondents were determined through sampling, specifically random sampling to establish randomness and maintain scientific rigor in the study. This method is a statistical technique where a sample is selected from a population such that each member of the population has an equal probability of being chosen. Random sampling allows researcher to make valid inferences and conclusions about a larger group based on data collected from a smaller, randomly selected subset. Thus, it provides an unbiased

representation of the overall population and reduces sampling bias (Taylor, 2023).

The sampling method used in this study was particularly appropriate because the respondents, which were the faculty members of the teacher education, criminology, and agriculture programs of Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology (KCAST), were randomly selected, ensuring that all instructors in those programs had an equal chance of being chosen for the sample. The researcher obtained first a formal permission from the college's Human Resource Department to access the population of instructors in those three academic programs. Then, the data was gathered about the full population of faculty in those programs, and this data was provided it to a statistician to compute the appropriate sample size, allowing them to obtain a representative sample of the target population and make valid inferences as well as eliminate potential biases.

The study was conducted among instructors teaching in the KCAST board programs. The institution has a total of 45 education instructors, 31 criminology instructors and 16 agriculture instructors. The sample appropriate for the study was computed by the statistician, which include 37 out of 45 instructors of teacher education, 25 out of 31 instructors of criminology and 13 out of 16 instructors of agriculture program. Out of 75 instructors, 92 were randomly picked as respondents of the study. Through varying a significant portion of the instructors, the study aimed to capture a comprehensive understanding of the results in these diverse fields.

Table 1.1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>Year Level</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Teacher Education	45	37	38.87%
Criminology	31	25	27.47%
Agriculture	16	13	14.18%
Total	92	75	81.52%

Qualitative Phase

In contrast, subject selection in qualitative research was purposeful. Purposive sampling is a non-probability sampling technique where the researcher intentionally selects participants based on their specific characteristics or attributes that are relevant to the research question, with the goal of gathering in-depth insights on a specific topic or phenomenon, rather than aiming for statistical representativeness of the broader population. The sample is selected based on the research objectives rather than availability and accessibility, though the findings may not be generalizable to the entire population (Nikolopoulou, 2023).

Only 14 participants equitably divided among teacher education, criminology and agriculture instructors were enjoined in the qualitative phase. All of them were instructors of the same college who participated in the in-depth interviews for the qualitative data gathering procedure. The study's focus on instructors from teacher education, criminology, and agriculture programs who had been working at the institution for at least 2-3 years ensured that the participants had sufficient experiences and knowledge to provide valuable insights about the research topic. These criteria were designed to exclude faculty members with less than 2 years of experience, thereby enhancing the depth and quality of the data collected. Participation was voluntary, and it was crucial that these participants were not involved in the quantitative phase of data collection, ensuring an unbiased perspective in the qualitative analysis. This careful selection process aimed to gather rich, informed perspectives that could contribute to the objectives.

Table 1.2. *Profiles of the Participants*

<i>Assigned Code</i>	<i>Program Instructor</i>
IDI- 01	Education
IDI- 02	Education
IDI- 03	Criminology
IDI- 04	Criminology
IDI- 05	Education
IDI- 06	Education
IDI- 07	Criminology
IDI- 08	Criminology
IDI- 09	Agriculture
IDI- 10	Agriculture
IDI- 11	Education
IDI- 12	Education
IDI- 13	Agriculture
IDI- 14	Agriculture

Instrument

Adapted research instruments refer to tools or measures that have been deliberately modified or customized to suit a specific research context, population, or language, rather than using them directly as originally developed. The difference from adopting an instrument is that it involves steps such as translating, modifying, adjusting response options to ensure the tool remains relevant and meaningful for the new research setting and participants. Thus, the process of adapting an instrument is aimed at enhancing its validity and reliability, ensuring that it accurately captures the intended data and resonates with the target population, thereby providing more

accurate and meaningful research outcomes (Teshome, 2023).

Quantitative Phase

In identifying the independent variable, differentiated instruction strategies, a questionnaire called Differentiated Instruction Survey was administered. This questionnaire was the one proposed by Robins and Georgia (2007). The said questionnaire had the following indicators: lesson design and implementation, content, procedures, communication, and learning.

On the other hand, in identifying the dependent variable respondents', Learner Empowerment Scale, a questionnaire that was intended to measure the learner empowerment was administered. This questionnaire was the one proposed by Frymier et al. (1996). The said questionnaire had the following indicators: impact, meaningfulness, and competence.

Both adapted questionnaires were five-point Likert scale, where participants only required to rate and tick one number from 1-5 in each item, with 1 being the lowest and 5 being the highest rating possible among the concerned respondents. According to Bhandari (2020), the five-point Likert scale is a widely used measurement tool in surveys and research, crucial for assessing respondents' attitudes, opinions, or behaviors. This scale enhances data collection by providing a clear, quantifiable way to capture subjective opinions, making it easier to analyze and interpret results statistically.

Differentiated Instruction. The adapted questionnaire demonstrates strong reliability and credibility, with consistent Cronbach's alpha values across indicators. Two factors of the variable, lesson design and implementation, retained 9 of 10 original items, achieving a Cronbach's α of 0.71. Meanwhile, another factor, content scale, retained all ten items, yielding a Cronbach's α of 0.76. Two more factors of the variable, procedure scale and learning scale, generated lower reliability scores at 0.67 and 0.63, respectively, but retained all original items. Then communication scale, the last factor of the variable, retained all eight items but exhibited low reliability with a Cronbach's α of 0.48. Overall, the results suggest that the questionnaire effectively measures the intended constructs, although one factor which is communication scale may require further evaluation.

The respondents were asked to evaluate their experiences by selecting a single rating on a scale from one to five, where one (lowest) represented rarely manifested and five (highest) indicated always manifested. This straightforward approach allowed participants to clearly express the frequency of their experiences, providing valuable insights in measuring the level of differentiated instruction among the faculty of KCAST board programs.

Learner Empowerment. Similarly, the adapted questionnaire exhibits strong reliability and credibility, as evidenced by the consistency of Cronbach's alpha values across all indicators or dimensions. Impact, one dimension of the variable, retained 16 items and scored maintained adequate internal consistency as measured by Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.95$. Second indicator, meaningfulness, also retained its ten original items and yielded an acceptable Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.94$. Lastly, the indicator which is competence retained all of its original nine items and yielded high reliability as can be seen in its Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.89$. Overall, the results suggest that the questionnaire effectively measures the intended constructs.

The respondents were asked to evaluate their experiences by selecting a single rating on a scale from one to five, where one (lowest) represented rarely manifested and five (highest) indicated always manifested. This straightforward approach allowed participants to clearly express the frequency of their experiences, providing valuable insights in measuring the level of learner empowerment among the faculty of KCAST board programs.

Qualitative Phase

As to the qualitative phase, a set of researcher-made grand tour questions was devised by the researcher and validated by the panel of experts. This was a set of open-ended questions that was developed based on the results of the survey. This was used as a compass for the in-depth interviews. Of all the participants who answered the survey questionnaire in the previous phase, none of them were purposively selected to undergo the IDI. Instead, the data gathering procedure for the qualitative phase of the study focused on another set of 14 participants. In particular, interviews were done which are suitable in gleaning insights, stories, experiences, opinions and other useful information.

Procedure

There were several steps in the data collection process. The following procedures were followed during the conduct of the study: From the time when the researcher is done with the routing of the manuscript to its panelists, the research manuscript is submitted to the Research Ethics of Kapalong College of Agriculture Science and Technology to check whether the study follows the mandated protocol needed for the ethical consideration and trustworthiness of the study. Also, the researcher requested for the ethics clearance to conduct the study. Then, after conforming to the recommendations as per protocol evaluation given by the Research Ethics Committee (REC) of the institution, the following were the stages to be done by the researcher in gathering the data needed in the study.

First, the researcher wrote a letter asking permission to conduct the study. A request letter was signed by the adviser attached with an endorsement letter signed by the College President of the Kapalong College of Agriculture Science and Technology. Afterwards, the approval of the college president entailed that the researcher can start gathering the data by distributing the survey questionnaire on the respondents.

Meanwhile, before gathering the data from the respondents, the researcher requested gatekeeper in KCAST to assist in conducting the said study. There was an orientation conducted by the researcher making the gatekeepers to be fully aware about the nature and purpose of the study. Also, part of the orientation was to give the informed consent form to the gatekeepers. Then, they will assist the researcher in the conduct of the study by giving the informed consent form to the respondents in their designated school along with the researcher. After that, the researcher discussed and oriented the respondents as to the goal and purpose of the study as well as their roles which were stipulated in the informed consent form. After the orientation, the respondents signed the form which indicated that they fully understood the purpose and goal of the study. Thus, this was done to ensure that the participants volunteered to be part in the conduct of the study as the research respondents.

After these essential and necessary preliminaries in conducting the study, discussed below are the different essential and significant measures in gathering the data both in the qualitative and quantitative phase of the study. By which, in the data gathering process, optimum confidentiality of data is assured.

Quantitative Phase

In the quantitative phase, adapted questionnaires were used for examining the relationship and the level of differentiated instruction and learner empowerment among the faculty of KCAST board program offerings, particularly those instructors under the Institute of Teacher Education, Criminology Program, and Agriculture Program. It was administered to a group of instructors who worked at Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology. In addition, the researcher wrote a letter of request to the school administrator, asking an approval to conduct the study inside the KCAST campus. The results were tallied, computed and analyzed to corroborate with the results of the qualitative data. The qualitative and quantitative phases of the study were done simultaneously.

Qualitative Phase

For the qualitative phase, a one-on-one interview was conducted to the identified participants in order to gather the lived experiences and insights of these instructors under the KCAST board programs specifically instructors under the Institute of Teacher Education, Criminology Program, and Agriculture Program with regard to their diversity in terms of the implementation of differentiated instruction and learner empowerment. An interview guide was used for the in-depth interview. Hence, to ensure authenticity of selection, the researcher invited the participants by contacting each of them in person, and they were informed about the integral details of the interview such as the time set for everyone's convenience.

In addition, these interviews were conducted to thoroughly explore the relationship between differentiated instruction and learner empowerment. Fourteen instructors with 2-3 years of teaching experience were purposively selected for these interviews, ensuring a diverse range of perspectives. This qualitative approach not only enriched the understanding of how differentiated instruction can enhance student learning experiences but also highlighted the practical challenges and successes of instructor's face in implementing these strategies in the classroom.

Data Analysis

Data analysis is the systematic process of collecting, cleaning, transforming, describing, modeling, and interpreting data to extract useful insights and support decision-making. Below are the key steps such as data collection, exploratory data analysis, data transformation, and interpretation and visualization of results. The researcher ensure that the data is accurate, complete, and representative of the problem being studied.

Quantitative Phase

In the quantitative data analysis, descriptive statistics such as mean was used to measure the level of each indicator for each variable, while Pearson r , an inferential statistical tool, determined the relationship between differentiated instruction and learner empowerment among the faculty of KCAST board programs. According to Kenton (2022), Pearson r is widely used to assess the linear relationship and strength of association between variables, though a high correlation does not necessarily imply causation. In addition, survey data was collected, tallied, and analyzed using SPSS for descriptive and inferential statistics to ascertain the status of instructors under the Institute of Teacher Education, Criminology Program, and Agriculture Program.

Qualitative Phase

The researcher employed a rigorous qualitative data analysis approach, utilizing both coding and thematic analysis techniques to systematically examine the patterns and themes that emerged from the utterances and statements provided by the participants during the one-on-one interviews. The coding process entailed the careful labeling and organizing the qualitative data into discrete categories or codes that represented the basic topics, concepts, and ideas present in the raw data, using both inductive and deductive methods (Medelyan, 2024).

Building upon the coding process, the researcher then engaged in thematic analysis to identify broader, more abstract themes that brought together multiple related codes, capturing the deeper meaning, significance, and interconnections within the data, with the specific purpose of analyzing the relationship between differentiated instruction and learner empowerment among the faculty members of the KCAST board programs. The data was carefully and rigorously analyzed to extract the most relevant and insightful themes,

which shed valuable light on the research objectives, providing rich, contextualized insights into the participants' experiences, perceptions, and perspectives within this educational context. Additionally, it allows the researcher to draw meaningful conclusions from the qualitative data and enhance the depth and quality of the research findings.

Ethical Considerations

To maintain the trust of the board program instructors at KCAST, this study placed paramount importance on their safety, anonymity, full protection, and confidentiality. Steps were meticulously taken that addressed these ethical considerations, with the aim of maintaining the confidence of the participants throughout the duration of the research.

These principles guided the conduct of the study in both qualitative and quantitative in a responsible and respectful manner, prioritizing the rights and well-being of the participants (Mack et al., 2005). Hence, measures were taken to ensure that these ethical considerations were carefully addressed throughout the course of a mixed method study. Further, the research of the study adhered with the elements of ethics which was stated from the International Ethical Guidelines for Health-Related Research Involving Humans in 2016.

Respect for persons was a fundamental ethical principle that underscored the significance of treating research participants with politeness and consideration, while recognizing their independence in deciding their involvement in a study (Munhall, 2012; Scott, 2013). This principle required furnishing participants with comprehensive information about the study, which ensured their clear comprehension of the research, as well as any potential risks or benefits involved in the research process. Obtaining informed consent constituted a pivotal component of abiding by this principle, signifying a voluntary agreement grounded in an informed comprehension. Through upholding the principle of respect for persons, the researcher guaranteed that the study was conducted ethically and in a manner that respected the rights and autonomy of the participants.

Prior to conducting the interviews, the researcher secured the participants' consent and prearranged the interview schedule to prevent any conflicts with their academic commitments or other responsibilities. This proactive approach aimed to minimize any disruptions to the schedules of the participants caused by the researcher's presence and to mitigate the necessity of rescheduling or canceling the interviews.

Throughout the course of my study, the researcher fostered a considerate and polite rapport with the participants, seeking their consent before recording our conversations. If they would not allow the recording of the conversation, the researcher truthfully respected his/her decision. Likewise, the researcher encouraged the participants to pose questions whenever they wished and upheld the confidentiality of both the in-depth interviews and the focus group discussion. Participants had the option to decline answering sensitive questions and the free will to withdraw from the study without facing any consequences. The researcher maintained an ethical and respectful study approach by building positive relationships and conducting myself with courtesy.

Consent constituted a pivotal element of research ethics, which served to demonstrate respect for research participants. Through the learning of informed consent, participants were comprehensively apprised of the aims and rationale of the research in which they were invited to engage. Written consent was diligently procured from each participant, affirming their willingness to partake in the in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. Additionally, participants received detailed information about the study's outcomes and discoveries, thereby upholding transparency and ensuring that they remained well-informed throughout the research process (Creswell, 2012).

To uphold the ethical standards of the study, the researcher furnished participants with permission and consent letters that comprehensively delineated the particular details of the study, including its methods, design, procedures, benefits, and risks. These letters were designed to facilitate comprehension of the participants on the nature of the study and empowered them to make informed decisions regarding their participation. Those who chose not to participate would be free to do so without any obligation to provide explanations, and they received assurances that their data would be held with strict confidentiality. Furthermore, participants were informed of their right to receive the results of the study. By adhering to these ethical guidelines, the researcher ensured that the study was conducted responsibly and respectfully.

Benevolence, as an ethical principle, underscored the dedication to mitigating risks and optimizing the welfare of research participants. In this study, measures were taken to safeguard and shield the well-being of the participants. The confidentiality of the interviewees was meticulously preserved to avert any potential threats to their privacy. Additionally, all data files were securely stored and never left unattended or inadequately protected (Bricki & Green, 2007).

To align with the principle of benevolence, the researcher implemented measures to preserve the anonymity and confidentiality of the responses and personal information of the participants. Also, the participants and respondents involved were informed of the findings to help them improve and enhance their language exposure and language competence, as one of the benefits of the study. Also, they were given tokens of appreciation to show respect and generosity on the time and efforts they gave in the study. To mitigate and avoid potential risks, the researcher opted for remote communication through a social media platform, avoiding face-to-face interactions with the participants. These precautions were undertaken to safeguard the well-being and interests of the participants, underscoring dedication to ethical research standards.

Additionally, the data gathered during this research study was exclusively utilized for the specified research objectives. However, the

outcomes of the study may also be disseminated through various means, including presentations within the institution, publication in scientific forums or journals, and presentations at conferences, whether on a local, national, or international scale. The intent of the researcher in sharing the findings of the study contributed to the broader body of knowledge within the fields of education and language teaching.

Confidentiality was upheld through various techniques to protect the data, results, and findings, as well as to ensure the safety of participants. This encompassed concealing all personal information of the participants and refraining from disclosing them. Furthermore, all materials, including audio records, encoded transcripts, notes, soft and hard copies of data, and other related documents, were disposed of immediately after the data analysis was concluded (Maree & Westhuizen, 2007).

To protect the identity of the participants and ensured compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, the researcher used discrete coding to denote each set of responses of the participants. This measure involved carefully phrasing any information that could potentially identify the participants in terms of their name, gender, ethnicity, or employment/location to avoid violating their anonymity. By using proper coding and other measures, the researcher was able to protect the identity of the participants and ensure that their privacy was respected.

Justice pertains to ensuring fairness and equal opportunity for participation among the participants. As such, the researcher utilized random sampling for quantitative phase and purposive sampling techniques. Participants were not coerced into participating and were given the freedom to decline if they chose to do so. Justice was ensured by including only relevant utterances of the participants related to the research objectives and accurately transcribing them (Munhall, 2012; Scott, 2013).

In this study, it was upheld by ensuring that the rights of the participants who identified themselves as non-board program students were respected. Given that the study aimed to explore the writing proficiency of non-board program students, no rights of minor students were violated. In recognition of their contribution, they were duly credited for their involvement in the research, contributing to the overall success of the study.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the result of data in both quantitative and qualitative phase. The first phase deals with the quantitative part which it displays the status of the faculty of KCAST board programs and its variables which significantly predict the relationship between differentiated instruction and learner empowerment. The second phase deals with the qualitative part in which it is presented in matrices. Each referred matrix shows the responses of the participants on their challenges, coping mechanism, and insights in implementing differentiated instruction and securing learner empowerment among the students. Also, each of the matrix contains the issues probed, core ideas, codes or categories, essential themes, and the supporting theoretical perspectives. Further, another matrix shows the data integration of the salient quantitative and qualitative findings.

Status of Differentiated instruction and Learner Empowerment among the Faculty of KCAST Board Programs

The results of the survey of the two variables namely: differentiated instruction and learner empowerment, are presented here. Moreover, the overall mean, including the items with the highest and the lowest ratings per indicator was given.

Status of Differentiated Instruction

Shown in Table 2.1 is the response of the KCAST board program instructors, specifically those instructors under the Institute of Teacher Education, Criminology Program, and Agriculture Program. It obtained an overall mean score of 4.75 which has a descriptive equivalent of high. Such a high rating reflects the instructors' effectiveness in catering educational experiences to meet the diverse needs of the students, thereby enhancing the overall learning environment and fostering academic success of the students. The independent variable of the study which is differentiated instruction has five indicators: lesson design and implementation, content, procedures, communication, and learning.

Table 2.1. *Level of Differentiated Instruction*

<i>Variables and Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
A. Lesson Design and Implementation		
1. Designing a lesson that engages students as members of the learning process	4.79	Very High
2. Crafting lessons that encourages students to seek and value alternative modes of investigation or problem solving	4.73	Very High
3. Focusing and directing my lesson which are often determined by ideas originating with students	4.71	Very High
4. Assessing the knowledge of my students through paper and pencil test	4.68	Very High
5. Using multisensory teaching approaches	4.69	Very High
Category Mean	4.69	Very High
B. Content		
1. Involving to my lessons, the fundamental concepts of the subjects	4.89	Very High
2. Crafting my lessons to promote coherent conceptual understanding	4.87	Very High
3. Utilizing solid grasp of the subject matter content inherent in the lessons	4.85	Very High
4. Promoting individualized instruction as much as possible	4.71	Very High

5. Expecting students to take ownership of their learning.	4.80	Very High
Category Mean	4.82	Very High
C. Procedures		
1. Creating a PowerPoint presentation to serve as a resource for students' notes	4.85	Very High
2. Promoting cooperative learning by having differentiated instruction	4.77	Very High
3. Implementing peer tutoring activity to my students	4.37	Very High
4. Matching my teaching practices to the needs of the students	4.79	Very High
5. Instructing my students to take notes when I am lecturing	4.51	Very High
Category Mean	4.66	Very High
D. Communication		
1. Asking my students during my discussion to trigger divergent modes of thinking	4.76	Very High
2. Using differentiated instruction in my lesson's activities	4.69	Very High
3. Focusing and directing the classroom discourse to the students' questions and comments	4.77	Very High
4. Encouraging students to respect each other and their opinions	4.91	Very High
5. Believing that students should have voice in my classroom	4.92	Very High
Category Mean	4.81	Very High
E. Learning		
1. Developing the needs of the students in their learning process	4.84	Very High
2. Utilizing tutoring to students who are struggling in learning	4.49	Very High
3. Assessing regularly to know what my students already know and what are the things they need to know	4.84	Very High
4. Describing myself with this metaphor "teacher as listener"	4.76	Very High
5. Acting as the resource person, working to support and enhance students learning	4.88	Very High
Category Mean	4.76	Very High
Overall Mean	4.75	Very High

Lesson Design and Implementation. In terms of lesson design and implementation, the category mean is 4.69 which has a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that it is always manifested by the faculty of KCAST board programs, specifically those instructors under the Institute of Teacher Education, Criminology Program, and Agriculture Program. Among the items under this indicator, item number 1- Designing a lesson that engages students as members of the learning process, got the highest mean of 4.79 which has a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that it is always manifested by the instructors.

On the other hand, the lowest item rated by the respondents was the item number 4- Assessing the knowledge of my students through paper and pencil test, with a mean of 4.68. This rating has a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that it is always manifested by the board program instructors.

Content. The content was rated by the participants which has a descriptive equivalent of very high, with a category mean of 4.82. This means that it is always manifested by the board program instructors. Item number 1- Involving to my lessons the fundamental concepts of the subjects, garnered the highest rating of 4.89 which has a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that it is always manifested by the board program instructors. Conversely, item number 4- Promoting individualized instruction as much as possible, got the lowest mean of 4.71 which has a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that it is always manifested by the board program instructors.

Procedure. The procedure got the category mean of 4.66 which has a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that it is always manifested by the board program instructors. The item number 1- Creating a PowerPoint presentation to serve as a resource for students' notes, got the highest mean of 4.85 which has a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that it is always manifested by the board program instructors. Meanwhile, item number 5- Instructing my students to take notes when I am lecturing, is the lowest rated item with the category mean of 4.51 which has a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that it is always manifested by the board program instructors.

Communication. In terms of communication, the category mean is 4.81 which has a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that it is always manifested by the board program instructors. The highest rated item is number 5- Believing that students should have voice in my classroom, which has a category mean of 4.92 which has a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that it is always manifested by the board program instructors. On the other hand, item number 2- Using differentiated instruction in my lesson's activities, got the lowest category mean of 4.69 which has a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that it is always manifested by the board program instructors.

Learning. In the context of learning, the category mean is 4.76 which has a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that it is always manifested by the respondents. The highest rated item is number 5- Acting as the resource person, working to support and enhance students learning, which garnered the category mean of 4.88 which has a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that it is always manifested by the board program instructors. Conversely, item number 2- Utilizing tutoring to students who are struggling in learning, got the lowest mean of 4.49 which has a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that it is always manifested by the board program instructors.

Status of Learner Empowerment

Shown in Table 2.2 were the responses of the KCAST board program instructors, specifically those instructors under the Institute of Teacher Education, Criminology Program, and Agriculture Program. It obtained an overall mean score of 4.80 which has a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the instructors under the KCAST board programs always manifested certain behaviors to promote learner empowerment. The independent variable of the study which is learner empowerment has three indicators: impact, meaningfulness, and competence.

Impact. In terms of impact, the category mean is 4.80 which has a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that it is always manifested by the board program instructors. Among the items under this indicator, item number 5- Encouraging students to contribute to the learning of others in the class, got the highest mean of 4.85 which has a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that it is always manifested by the board program instructors. On the other hand, the lowest item rated by the participants was item number 4- Making an impact on the way things run in my class, with a mean of 4.75 which has a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that it is always manifested by the board program instructors.

Meaningfulness. The meaningfulness was rated by the participants and it has a descriptive equivalent of high, as evidenced in its category mean of 4.80. This means that it is always manifested by the board program instructors. Among the items under with this indicator, item number 1- Expressing genuine appreciation to my students when they participate actively in the class, garnered the highest category mean of 4.87 which has a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that it is always manifested by the board program instructors. Contrary to this one, item number 5- Requiring personally meaningful task that hold personal significance towards my students, got the lowest mean of 4.73 which has a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that it is always manifested by the board program instructors.

Table 2.2. Level of Learner Empowerment

<i>Variables and Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
A. Impact		
1. Making a difference in how things are done in my class	4.80	Very High
2. Choosing the methods I can use to perform my work	4.81	Very High
3. Utilizing alternative approaches to learning to encourage the class	4.80	Very High
4. Making an impact on the way things run in my class	4.75	Very High
5. Encouraging students to contribute to the learning of others in the class	4.85	Very High
Category Mean	4.80	Very High
B. Meaningfulness		
1. Expressing genuine appreciation to my students when they participate actively in the class	4.87	Very High
2. Requiring personally meaningful task that hold personal significance towards my students	4.73	Very High
3. Considering the task I have required in my class to be valuable to my students	4.79	Very High
4. Utilizing information that is useful in my class	4.84	Very High
5. Requiring necessary skills to my students to perform successfully in class	4.79	Very High
Category Mean	4.80	Very High
C. Competence		
1. Believing in my capabilities to achieve empowering learner in the class	4.81	Very High
2. Possessing the necessary skills to empower learners	4.81	Very High
3. Studying the lesson before having my session in class	4.75	Very High
4. Building confidence in my ability to successfully perform the task in the class	4.87	Very High
5. Feeling very competent in empowering students in their learning process	4.80	Very High
Category Mean	4.80	Very High
Overall Mean	4.80	Very High

Competence. In the context of competence, the category mean is 4.81 which has a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that it always manifested by the board program instructors. Under this indicator, item number 4- Building confidence in my ability to successfully perform the task in the class, garnered the high category mean of 4.87 which has a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that it is always manifested by the board program instructors. On the other hand, item number 3- Studying the lesson before having my session in class, got the lowest category mean of 4.75 which has a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that it is always manifested by the board program instructors.

Correlation between Differentiated Instruction and Learner Empowerment among the Faculty of KCAST Board Programs

Table 3.1 presents the results of the specific correlation analysis between the relationship of differentiated instruction and learner empowerment among the faculty members of KCAST board programs. A thorough examination of the data reveals that the perceived differentiated instruction ($M=4.75$) and learner empowerment ($M=4.80$) has a moderate positive correlation, as per the description of Cohen and Holliday (1983) on the range of different levels of correlation.

Reflected in the presented table was the result of the significant relationship between differentiated instruction and learner empowerment. The result illustrates the relationship of differentiated instruction and learning empowerment. The researcher is

measuring two parameters in this study, since the researcher estimates two relationships. The degree of freedom corresponds to the sample size (75) minus 2. Therefore, the $r(73) = .571$ indicates a moderately strong positive linear relationship between the two variables. This means that as one variable increase, the other variable tends to increase as well, but the relationship is not perfect. The closer the value to 1, the stronger the linear relationship between variables. This can be interpreted that 57% of the variance of differentiated instruction and learner empowerment and the remaining 43% is due to other variables not covered in the study. Since the p-value is less than the chosen significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected, supporting the conclusion that there is a significant relationship between differentiated instruction and learner empowerment.

Table 3.1. Significant Relationship between Differentiated Instruction and Learner Empowerment among The Faculty of KCAST Board Programs

Variable	Mean	R-Value	P-Value	Decision @=0.05
Differentiated Instruction	4.75			
Learner Empowerment	4.80	.571	<.001	Ho Rejected

Lived Experiences and Strategies of the Board Program Instructors in Implementing Differentiated Instruction and fostering Learner Empowerment

There are five essential themes which are created based on the in-depth interviews of the participants on the first research question. Before the presentation of the results of the interviews and discussions, profiles of the participants for the qualitative collection are presented in Table 1.2. The table represents the participants' profiles for the qualitative phase. They were selected purposively following the inclusion criteria: he or she must be a KCAST instructor under the following institute or board programs: Institution of Teacher Education, Criminology Program, and Agriculture Program, with at least 2 years of teaching experience. Based on the table, the profiles are divided into participants' program instructors.

Furthermore, Table 3.2 deals on the lived experiences and strategies of the board program instructors in the implementation of differentiated instruction and learner empowerment. The essential themes which emerged from the transcriptions of the participants' responses for the research question under the qualitative phase are consisted of overarching themes which are summarized in the said table.

Table 3.2. Lived Experiences and Strategies of the Board Program Instructors in Implementing Differentiated Instruction and fostering Learner Empowerment

Issue Probed	Core Ideas	Code/ Categories	Essential Themes	Theoretical Support
Impact of creating different learning approaches	Recognizing the different learner styles of the students and their different intelligences.	Recognition of Student Diversity	Recognition and Accommodation of Student Diversity to Enhance Pedagogy	Theory of Multiple Intelligences And Differentiated Instruction Theory
	Understanding the diversity of each student in the classroom.	Differentiated Instruction		
	Fostering differentiated instructions to cater to the different learning styles and preferences of the students.	Improvement of Teaching-Learning Process		
Catering Heterogeneous Learners inside the Classroom	Enhancing the learning process of the students by having differentiated instruction.		Equity and Inclusion in Education	Learning Styles Theory and Inclusive Education Theory
	Identifying applicable strategies and approaches to cater to the diverse students inside the classroom	Understanding Students' Needs and Preferences		
	Organizing things for effective teaching-learning process.	Creating an Inclusive Classroom Environment		
	Enabling students to continue learning with their own preference of learning.			
	Improving teaching-learning process through active student-centered learning and engaging activities.			
	Having difficulties in catering individual needs through not knowing the students' learning styles and preferences.			
	Having problems catering to the diverse students' needs in the classroom			
	Strategically fostering inclusive classroom environment in fostering a sense of belonging of the students' learning			
	Needing various strategies and teaching approaches in enhancing learning experiences of the diverse students			

The Effect of Time Constraints in Planning Differentiated Instruction and Learner Empowerment	Having problems due to time constraints in implementing various activities. Having difficulties in maximizing the time to effectively target learning goals outcomes of the students Needing enough time for planning differentiated instruction and learner empowerment strategies. Balancing act of time allocation in planning differentiated instruction to cater to diverse students' needs. Strategically prioritizing learning objectives and instructional approaches within time-constrained time frames.	Time Management Challenges	Effective Time Management in Education	Educational Time Management Theory
Utilization of Group and Collaborative Learning in the Teaching - Learning Process	Engaging students in group activities and collaborative tasks to enhance learning experiences. Encouraging collaboration and teamwork from other students to support students' diverse needs. Developing communication skills through collaborative learning. Promoting active engagement through effectively working with teams and collaborating towards common goals.	Time Allocation and Planning	Collaborative Learning for Inclusive Engagement	Social Constructivism Theory
Learning standard and the Needs of Students in the Classroom	Supporting diverse learning needs by allowing students to learn from each other's strengths and experiences Difficulties in adjusting learning standards without compromising the learning process Having difficulties with changes in the actual implementation of differentiated instruction that will empower learners. Compromising the teacher's standards just to meet the needs of the students without compromising their learning. Strategically giving consideration based on the students' ability and capability to achieve certain lesson outcomes Having consideration for the students in meeting the teacher's learning standards.	Engagement and Collaboration	Harmonizing Academic Standards and Students' Diverse Needs	Zone of Proximal Development Theory
		Supporting Diverse Learning Difficulties in Adjusting Learning Standards		
		Considering Student Abilities and Capabilities		

Recognition and Accommodation of Student Diversity to Enhance Pedagogy. In the context of the implementation of differentiated instruction and learner empowerment, some experiences encountered by the board program instructors is recognizing and accommodating the diversity of the students in the classroom in terms of varying the teaching approaches and strategies to enhance and develop the learning process and product of the students.

Impact of creating different learning approaches of the instructors. This is the first code of the probed on the first probed issue. Instructors under board programs expresses common responses on the recognition and accommodation of student diversity to enhance pedagogy. Most of them stated that the diversity of the students in the classroom can affect the teaching approaches and strategies to accommodate this different learning needs of the students that will enhance not just their learning experience but to the enhance pedagogy as well.

Similarly, Participant 1 recognized that they may experience modifying teaching approaches and strategies to cater, recognize, and accommodate student's diversity to enhance the learning experiences of the students to empower them. Participant 1 emphasizes that in order to empower the learners, instructors or teacher must varied the teaching approaches and strategies not just to enhance the teaching pedagogy but to the holistic learning of the students as well. Additionally, when the teacher varied their strategies and approaches in teaching they can effectively recognize and accommodate the diversity of the students. He stated that:

“Okay... now of course since you are... not mandated but you are... you have to because that's part of your teaching career that you have to ensure differentiated instruction to address this different needs of the students. I really have to ensure that I would be utilizing different strategies okay.” (IDI-01)

(Though it is not explicitly required, it is essentially a must-do because it is an integral part of being a teacher— since it is a crucial

part of your teaching career to ensure differentiated instruction to address the different needs of the students, I must ensure that I am utilizing various strategies.)

Additionally, Participant 1 recognizing that to better recognize and accommodate the diversity of the learners to empower them instructors must have a holistic understanding towards the diversity of the students in the classroom, and this primarily involve resources that is fit and appropriate to the different learning preferences of the students. He additionally stated that:

“And another challenge for me is... the available resources, because... the school do not, although the school have resources or facilities but it is... I considered it as one of my greatest challenge challenges because I really need to extend my free service.” (IDI-01)

(Another challenge for me is the availability of resources. Although the school does have resources or facilities, I consider it one of my greatest challenges.)

Differentiated Instruction. This is the second code for the first probed issue. The participant imparted that they constantly struggling with the implementation of differentiated instruction including different strategies, approaches, teaching resources, and lessons' activities. Having trouble in modifying the strategies and approaches in the learning process can impede the holistic development of the learners.

Instructors often face challenges in modifying their strategies and approaches when providing instruction due to the varying and changing needs of students. Each student is unique, with their own learning styles, preferences, and challenges, making it difficult for instructors to cater to everyone simultaneously. Additionally, instructors must constantly evaluate and refine their teaching techniques to ensure the effectiveness of their instruction. As Participant 1 stated:

“I really have to ensure that I would be utilizing different strategies okay, not only individualized strategies but I have to ensure that I can use a mixture of strategies not only individualized but group basis strategies and performance-based strategies.” (IDI-01)

(I need to ensure that I am utilizing a variety of strategies. Not only individualized strategies, but also a mix that includes group-based and performance-based strategies.)

Moreover, different strategies in the teaching-learning process are one of the major factors that instructors must consider in the classroom setting since students are diverse in nature various instruction might help the teachers to accommodate the different learning preferences of the students. This will help instructors to empower the learners because through various strategies in teaching including differentiated instruction, activities, materials and resources will help to better accommodate and empower the learners. As Participant 5 stated that,

“We need to make or learning process interesting in terms of implementing this differentiated instruction and of course learner empowerment must be followed by differentiated learning your teaching strategy must be varied in terms of what kind of students or who are your students so that's how it works, you really need to innovate, creative, and if possible, you need to be observant enough to see this kind of strategy.” (IDI-05)

(We need to make the learning process interesting by implementing differentiated instruction, ensuring that learner empowerment is followed by differentiated learning. Your teaching strategy must vary according to the needs and characteristics of your students. That is how it works. You really need to innovate, be creative, and, if possible, be observant enough to identify the most effective strategies.)

Improvement of Teaching-Learning process. This is the third code for the first probed issue. The participants shared that as they navigate all the challenges that they have faced in implementing of differentiated instruction and learner empowerment it is crucial to considerate the improvement of the teaching-learning process. Understanding differentiated instruction to empower learners will help the instructors to better recognize and accommodate the diverse learners' needs.

With that being said, instructors really consider the factor that they really need to make constant improvements in the context of the teaching-learning process to ensure that learners will be empower. Embracing a mindset of continuous improvement allows instructors to adapt to the evolving needs of diverse learners, incorporate new technologies and resources, and create dynamic learning environments that foster engagement, critical thinking, and the acquisition of knowledge and skills. As Participant 2 stated that:

“So mao tu akong ingon gaina nga gina reinforce namo sila ug kadalasan gina pa practice namo sila ug memorization aron ma develop ilang critical thinking skillsmao tu gina paningkamutan namo nga di sila mag lisud at the same time kami sad, as instructor, makita namo nga naa jud silay natun-an, tung mga slow learners wala gyud.” (IDI-02)

(So, as I mentioned earlier, we reinforce their learning by frequently practicing memorization to develop their critical thinking skills. We strive to ensure they do not struggle, and at the same time, as instructors, we can see that they are indeed learning. However, most of the slow learners still struggle.)

Similarly, instructors must consider their students in terms of having these differentiated instructions. By implementing differentiated instruction techniques, teachers can provide appropriate challenges and support for each student to help them reach their full potential. Thus, considering such that instructors must create a comfortable learning environment to develop teaching-learning process. As participant 3 stated that:

“In applying differentiated instruction, I would say, it would probably give me more insights, information as to how I make improve my teaching strategy in teaching activities since during that implementation of differentiate instruction I would able to get to know what are the weaknesses, what aspect they are good at it so I could modify it on the next meeting.” (IDI-03)

(In implementing differentiated instruction, I would say that it would likely provide me with more insights and information on how to improve my teaching strategies in various activities. Through the implementation of differentiated instruction, I would be able to identify weaknesses and strengths among my students, allowing me to adjust my approach accordingly in future sessions.)

Equity and Inclusion in Education. In the context of implementing differentiated instruction and learner empowerment. The faculty of KCAST board programs experiencing difficulties in catering individual needs of the students through not knowing the students' learning styles and preferences as well as instructors are having problems in terms of catering the diverse students' needs in the classroom. This will lead on how the instructors will develop equity and inclusion inside the classroom. Most of the participants are having the same problem in implementing differentiated instruction and learner empowerment.

Understanding Students' Needs and Preferences. This is the first code of the second for the second probe or issue. When instructors demonstrate genuine understanding and consideration, they foster trust, respect, and empowerment, motivating students to take an active role in their learning by setting goals and making choices. In addition, understanding students' needs is the foundation for creating a responsive, engaging, and inclusive learning environment that promotes the success of all learners. The participants mentioned that in order to better accommodate differentiated instruction and learner empowerment first things that an instructor must do is to understand the students' needs and learning preferences.

In connection with that, instructors must know the strength and weaknesses of the students to modify the kind of strategies and approaches that they need to implement in the classroom. Additionally, knowing the learning preferences of the students will also help to better cater the diverse learners in the classroom. By identifying the unique characteristics and needs of each student, teachers can create a more inclusive and engaging learning environment that caters to diverse learners. As participant 1 stated that:

“In terms of recognizing the styles, learning styles and learning preferences of my students so what I the pure, so because of that although it is a short period of time, I can be given chance talaga to get to know them and through that, I can device effective strategies and instructions to them.” (IDI-01)

(In terms of recognizing the learning styles and preferences of my students, what I did was ensure that our first meeting focused on establishing rapport. Through this process, I gained insight into their learning styles and preferences. Despite the short duration of this initial interaction, I was able to truly get to know them and devise effective strategies and instructions.)

Additionally, participant 10 recognize that understanding the differences of the students in the classroom including their learning preferences and styles will help the instructors to modify their teaching strategies and approaches. This knowledge allows instructors to tailor their lessons, activities, and assessments to match the preferred learning styles of their students and develop their holistic learning experience. Participant 10 additionally stated that:

“It is really difficult to implement this differentiated instruction since you have this... what do you call this one, heterogeneous types of students or group of students, when we talk about heterogeneous they are different from one another, they have different skills, different learning styles the most important think we must consider as a teacher and we do different instruction because we wanted to target, we wanted to achieve the needs of these students with their different styles, different strategies in learning as well.” (IDI-10)

(Implementing differentiated instruction is challenging because of the heterogeneous nature of the students. When we talk about heterogeneous groups, we mean that students are different from one another, they have varying skills and learning styles. As teachers, the most important thing to consider is addressing these differences. We use differentiated instruction to meet the diverse needs of students, employing various strategies and approaches to cater to their individual learning styles.)

Moreover, Instructors face significant challenges in catering to the diverse needs of their students due to the dynamic nature of learning preferences. With students coming from various backgrounds, cultures, and experiences, it becomes increasingly difficult for instructors to modify their teaching approaches to accommodate individual learning styles. As participant 9 stated that:

“To effectively implement differentiated instruction and empower learners, instructors should understand diverse learning styles to tailor their teaching and develop strong communication skills to foster a positive, collaborative classroom environment.” (IDI-09)

(To effectively implement differentiated instruction and empower learners, instructors should understand diverse learning styles to tailor their teaching and develop strong communication skills to foster a positive, collaborative classroom environment.)

Creating an Inclusive Classroom Environment. This is the second code for the second probed issue. Participants mentioned that it is necessary to create an inclusive classroom environment that involves various teaching strategies and teaching approaches that will cater the diverse learning needs of students, thereby fostering a sense of belonging and enhancing their learning experiences will provide strong foundation to enhance the overall learning experiences of the diverse students.

Similarly, the difficulties encountered by the instructors under the faculty of teacher education, criminology, and agriculture. This

challenge continued as learning is not stagnant, hence, it is a gradual process that is need to develop from time to time to enhance the learning experiences of the students. They also navigate the complexities of diverse student populations, varying learning styles, and the unique challenges posed by each discipline. As participant 4 stated that:

“I find it difficult what particular strategy that I will going to use since I know from the very beginning that in a certain classroom, diverse students are found so there for I need to look for particular strategy or particular instruction where I could be able to get or the needs of those students.” (IDI-04).

(I find it difficult to decide on a particular strategy to use, knowing that a classroom contains diverse students. Therefore, I need to identify a specific strategy or instruction that can effectively meet the needs of all these students.)

Additionally, participant 8 recognize that implementing differentiated instruction is crucial in empowering learners in the teaching-learning process. To achieve this, instructors must promote an inclusive classroom environment that promotes diversity, fosters a sense of belonging, and encourages active participation from all students. By creating a safe and supportive space where learners feel valued, respected, and heard, instructors can help them develop confidence, take risks, and embrace their unique strengths and learning styles. As participant 8 additionally stated that:

“So, with that changes may occur in terms with the teaching strategies since our goal is to cater man the needs of our diverse students so in order to cater the needs of our diverse students, we need to have this differentiated instruction, strategies, and approaches for us to be able na ma target ang learning outcomes ana nga specific lesson.” (IDI-08)

(Changes may occur in terms of teaching strategies because our aim is to address the needs of our diverse students. Therefore, in order to address the needs of our diverse students, we need to employ differentiated instruction, strategies, and approaches to target the specific learning outcomes of each lesson.)

Effective Time Management in Education. In the context of implementing differentiated instruction and learner empowerment the faculty of KCAST board programs is having difficulty with time constraints which makes it challenging to implement differentiated instruction while also optimizing the time available to properly target student learning outcomes. This difficulty includes the need for adequate time to develop customized education and strategies targeted at empowering students. Finding a balance between meeting curriculum standards and catering to students' different needs within the limited time available is a major challenge for the instructors under board programs.

Time Management Challenges. This is the first code for third probed issue. Many of the participants shared their experience in terms of the time constraints in implementing differentiated instruction and learner empowerment. Due to the time constraints many activities have have been compromise and cannot be implement since the time is limited and it is difficult for the instructors to maximize the time considering that they need to cater the diverse needs of the diverse students in the classroom. They believed that time is really a big factor in implementing differentiated instruction as well as empowering learners.

In addition, it is of the utmost importance to allow a sufficient amount of time within a single semester to understand and acknowledge the students' different backgrounds, cultures, and learning styles. Creating differentiated instructions for each student in one class requires careful planning and allocation of time to generate appropriate activities and materials, making time management a substantial barrier to meeting the student's needs. As participant 1 stated that:

“One of my greatest challenge since I am, I have to deal with the different learning styles and preferences of my students is time because you have to really ensure that you have enough time to get to know and recognize of course the different learning styles, the background and the culture, so for me, time is indeed one of the greatest challenges.” (IDI-01).

(One of my most significant challenges, given that I must address the diverse learning styles and preferences of my students, is time. It's crucial to ensure I have enough time to understand and acknowledge their various learning styles, backgrounds, and cultures, especially considering we only have one semester to engage with our students. Managing time effectively is a considerable challenge in getting to know my students well)

Moreover, Instructors must carefully consider how to maximize and make the most of every minute when implementing differentiated instruction and empowering learners. This requires thoughtful planning to provide a variety of engaging learning experiences tailored to diverse student needs, interests, and abilities. Instructors should strategically structure lessons to allow students to learn at their own pace, explore topics in depth, and take ownership of their learning. As participant 5 stated that:

“Time is really a factor in implementing this differentiated instruction in empowering learners, your teaching strategies must be varied from time to time.” (IDI-05)

(Time is a significant factor in implementing differentiated instruction to empower learners. Your teaching strategies need to be varied frequently to effectively address the diverse needs of students.)

Time Allocation and Planning. This is the second code for third probed issue. Majority of the participants shared their experienced in terms of effectively manage the time allocation. It is crucial when implementing differentiated instruction to meet the varied needs of

students to consider the time allocation and planning, this involves strategically prioritizing learning goals and various teaching strategies and approaches within restricted time frames. With that they believed that instructors must skillfully balance their time to ensure the needs of the diverse student are addressed, while optimizing overall learning outcomes in the classroom setting.

In that sense, implementing differentiated instruction presents significant challenges. These include the crucial planning is required to create modified activities, strategies or approaches in teaching for the diverse group in the classroom, as well as the competent execution and time management is required to assure efficient delivery within limited time periods. As Participant 7 stated that:

“Another challenge pud na akong na note nu is the time constraints so in implementing differentiated instruction you are really pressured to have the students present everything, have all groups present everything different activities or undergo different activities in not more than one hour kay ang tendency man gud ana kay masobraan ta ka overwhelm sa atung activities we exceed the time limit and of course there are no more extensions afforded to us so sayang ma defeat ang purpose sa differentiated instruction mao na akong mga challenges na-na note.” (IDI-07)

(Additionally, another challenge I noted is time constraints. Implementing differentiated instruction puts pressure on ensuring that students cover all activities within a limited timeframe. There's a risk of feeling overwhelmed with activities, exceeding the time limit, and no extensions are typically granted, which could undermine the purpose of differentiated instruction. These are the challenges I've observed.)

Additionally, Implementing differentiated instruction and learner empowerment is a time-consuming but essential process in the teaching-learning context. It requires a deep understanding of each student's unique needs, strengths, and learning preferences. However, this approach demands a significant investment of time and resources, as it involves creating multiple lesson plans, assessments, and learning materials to cater to diverse learners. As Participant 8 stated that:

“There is still time constraints in terms of how I craft my lessons like makaya ba siya karon na day or karon na week, it is achievable or challenging lang kaayo siya para sa mga students that is why I find it challenging the time constraints in preparing my instructional materials also the lesson itself.” (IDI-08)

(There are still time constraints in terms of how I plan my lessons, such as whether they can be accomplished within the current day or week, whether it is achievable or overly challenging for the students. That's why I find it challenging to manage the time constraints in preparing my instructional materials as well as the lessons itself.)

Moreover, adjusting the type of learning and teaching-learning strategies and approaches with the given time frames can be a struggle to the board program instructors. This implies the importance of flexibility and adaptability of the instructors in terms of planning and utilizing different teaching approaches and strategies to effectively utilize the available time for holistic student learning experiences. As participant 14 additionally stated that:

“And also here in KCAST the time constraints because there are subjects that you will going to teach one hour face to face lang and also there are subjects that you are going to teach one hour and thirty minutes every week so sometimes it is really a struggle to adjust the type of learning of the types of lesson you are going to deliver and how you are going to strategize on that.” (IDI-14)

(Here at KCAST, we face time constraints due to varying class durations. Some subjects are taught for just one hour of face-to-face instruction, while others have one hour and thirty minutes of class time per week. This often makes it challenging to adapt the learning approach and determine the appropriate lesson delivery strategies, requiring careful strategizing to ensure effective teaching within these constraints)

Collaborative Learning for Inclusive Engagement. In context of implementing differentiated instruction and learner empowerment of the instructors under the Board programs experiencing challenges in terms of having inclusive engagement in the classroom setting. Utilizing group and collaborative learning strategies in the teaching-learning process makes it more challenging since it is crucial for an instructor to create an interactive and engaging classroom environment. Most of the participants share the experiences of having difficulties in creating collaborative and inclusive engagement in the classroom setting.

Engagement and Collaboration. This is the first code for fourth probed issue. Many of the instructors under the institute of teacher education, criminology, and agriculture were having the same experiences in terms of making the classroom more engaging to empower the learners. Instructors must innovate their teaching strategies and approaches including classroom activities to enhance the learning process of the students as well their learning product.

In connection with that, instructors must be adaptive in different kinds of strategies in teaching learning process, instructors can encourage students to share ideas, cooperate on projects, and solve problems together. This provides a deeper comprehension of the subject by allowing students to learn from one another's opinions and experiences. As participant 3 stated that:

“Honestly, before when I was still a student I'm not used to group study or group activity because I most on independent learning, if you gonna ask what particular changes or change within myself so that to accommodate all their needs I will always involve my students in to interactive activity in such a thing that they will be assigned to a specific group randomly not just all the time they have the same grouping.” (IDI-03)

(Okay, honestly, when I was a student, I was not accustomed to group study or activities because I primarily focused on independent learning. However, as an educator now, I have made changes within myself to accommodate all my students' needs. I frequently involve them in interactive activities, where they are assigned to random groups to ensure they get to know one another and I can assess their differences.)

Additionally, group and collaborative learning strategies improve students' communication and teamwork skills, preparing them for real-world circumstances requiring collaboration. All things considered, incorporating collaborative and group learning approaches enhances the learning process and encourages all-encompassing learning goals. As Participant 14 additionally stated that:

“We are in the 21st century some students are very dynamic or they are very kanang lahi-lahi ilang style sa pag learn so I practice holistic learning for my students for them to be grasp well the lesson like gahatag ko ug mga activities like group activities to encourage them to collaborate their ideas to their classmates.” (IDI-14)

(We are in the 21st century where students have diverse learning styles. Therefore, I practice holistic learning for my students to grasp the lesson well. I provide activities like group activities to encourage them to collaborate and share ideas with their classmates.)

Supporting Diverse Learning. This is the first code for fourth probed issue. Many of the instructors under the institute of teacher education, criminology, and agriculture shared experience in terms of supporting diverse learning needs, instructors believe that it entails creating opportunities for students to benefit from each other's strengths and experiences. By fostering a collaborative learning environment, where students engage with peers of varied backgrounds and abilities, instructors can facilitate a rich exchange of ideas and knowledge.

In that sense, it encourages students to tap into their unique strengths while also learning from others who may excel in different areas. Embracing diversity in the classroom not only enhances academic outcomes but also promotes a deeper understanding and appreciation of different perspectives, ultimately enriching the overall learning experience for all students. As participant 2 stated that.

“Akong ginabuhat ana is gina mixed nako murag groupings, gina group nako sila para di nako mabilin jud tung slow jud namo.” (IDI-02)

(In my approach, I address the implementation by incorporating mixed groupings. This means I organize students into groups to prevent anyone from being left behind, particularly those who may struggle or progress more slowly.)

Additionally, participant 9 also recognize Incorporating a variety of group activities and learning approaches in the teaching-learning process can significantly contribute to the holistic development of learners, empowering them to reach their full potential. By engaging in collaborative tasks, learners develop essential skills such as communication, teamwork, and problem-solving, which are crucial for success in both academic and real-world settings. As she added that:

“I varied instruction materials, offering a range of materials and resources enables students to interact with content in various ways as an instructors, I must make adjustments to my teaching methods to better accommodate diverse learning styles and empower learners to accommodate a variety of learning styles, this include interactive internet materials, films, simulations, textbooks, group activities and modules.” (IDI-09)

(I vary instructional materials by offering a range of resources, enabling students to interact with content in diverse ways. As an instructor, I adjust my teaching methods to accommodate different learning styles and empower learners. This includes incorporating interactive internet materials, films, simulations, textbooks, group activities, and modules to cater to various learning preferences.)

Harmonizing Academic Standards and Students' Diverse Needs. In context of implementing differentiated instruction and learner empowerment of the instructors under the Board programs experiencing challenges in terms of harmonizing academic standards and students' diverse needs at the same time. Instructors find it difficult in aligning learning standards with the needs of students in the classroom since it is essential for instructors in fostering meaningful learning experiences of the students. By contextualizing the curriculum to address the diverse learning styles, backgrounds, and abilities of students, educators can ensure that instructional goals are relevant and achievable for all learners.

Difficulties in Adjusting Learning Standards. This is the first code for fifth probed issue. Many of the instructors under the institute of teacher education, criminology, and agriculture were having the same experiences in terms of adapting learning standards without compromising the learning process of the students and this must be addressed carefully. Similarly, using differentiated instruction to empower learners create challenges to the instructors under board programs.

In connection, effective teachers must employ a range of strategies, such as differentiated instruction, collaborative learning, and ongoing assessment, to create a learning environment that is both challenging and supportive. By fostering a culture of growth and embracing the complexities of the classroom, teachers can help students overcome obstacles, develop essential skills, and achieve their educational goals. As participant 3 stated that:

“It will depend now on how considerate you as a teacher for example you are observing class that they are doing their best however their best is not suit to your given standards in that case you will have a little bit adjustment like lower but not to the extent that it will

compromise their learning probably we will have this so-called normative standard.” (IDI-03)

(In such situations, it depends on how considerate you are as a teacher. For instance, if you observe that students are giving their best effort, but it does not quite meet your standards, you may need to make slight adjustments, but not to the extent that it undermines their learning. Perhaps you will refer to a normative standard, considering the average performance, and temporarily set aside your own standard.)

In that sense, instructors should do their best in terms of implementing differentiated instruction and learner empowerment. Instructors who are skilled in adjusting their methods while maintaining high standards create a balanced and enriching educational experience that promotes academic growth without compromising the overall learning outcomes of their students. As participant 5 has stated that:

“And then again as an instructor, di naman pwede na as an instructor or teacher then you will just let set your own standards and let your students reach your own standards mas mahirap yun, sometimes it is not an effective way to empower learners you really need to somehow meet half way kumbaga.” (IDI-05)

(“This flexibility in setting standards can be empowering as it allows us to meet students halfway, rather than rigidly adhering to our own standards, which may not always be effective in empowering learners.”)

Additionally, instructors must carefully consider the diverse capabilities and needs of their students when setting learning standards and objectives. This involves adapting instructional methods, materials, and assessments to accommodate individual differences, ensuring that all students have the opportunity to engage with the content and demonstrate their understanding. As participant 7 stated that:

“Of course, I set standards there are many instances in which I set the standards ba ahh dapat ing-ani jud na level ng akong gusto ma attain sa klase but to my disappointment nu the class could not measure up to it but sometimes it is the teacher factor nu and naa jud mga instances na ing-ana nu and it is quite normal that is why it is important to really know your students specially those katung ga hilom-hilom ra katung walay presence sa klase sila jud mostly ang dapat tutukan tana.” (IDI-07)

(Of course, I set standards. There are many instances where I establish the standards that I want the class to achieve, but to my disappointment, the class could not meet them. Sometimes, it is due to the teacher's influence, and there are indeed instances like that, which is quite normal. That is why it is crucial to truly understand your students, especially those who are quiet or lack presence in class, as they often require special attention.)

Considering Student Abilities and Capabilities. This is the second code for fifth probed issue. Many of the instructors under the institute of teacher education, criminology, and agriculture were having the same experiences in terms of strategically thinking about what each student can do and how they learn best. It's important for teachers to think about what students can do when deciding what they should learn, making sure it's something they can achieve but still challenges them.

In connection, it is crucial for educators to take into account students' needs and capabilities when setting learning standards, ensuring they are attainable yet challenging enough to promote growth and achievement. Through understanding the varying levels of knowledge, skills, and learning styles within their classrooms, instructors can create a more inclusive and effective teaching-learning environment. As participant 10 stated that:

“It does not mean that you have already that standard in you in teaching mao na gyud na siya ang standard na you need to follow there are times that you have to lower the standards as you modified the strategies or standards that you have set within you for you to be able to address the needs of the students because teaching is somehow spiral method that's needs to be gradual ba ang iyang process gikan sa basics padulong sa complex.” (IDI-10)

(Being flexible means not only adjusting to the attitudes and behavior in the classroom, but also adapting our teaching styles and strategies. Just because you have certain teaching standards does not mean you have to stick to them all the time. Sometimes, you have to lower your standards and change your strategies to meet the needs of your students. Teaching is like a spiral method, It needs to gradually progress from basics to more complex topics.)

Additionally, setting appropriate standards in the teaching-learning process requires carefully considering the diverse capabilities and needs of all learners in the classroom. Effective teachers recognize that students have a wide range of academic abilities, learning styles, backgrounds, and challenges. Thus, setting standards that are high yet achievable for each individual students, instructors can create an inclusive environment where all students are supported to reach their full potential. As participant 14 stated that:

“Though there are sometimes na dili na nila ma reach nga standards we tend to reinforced sa ilaha nga kailangan as a board program students because in my case I have taught criminology and teacher education so kailangan nату eh motivate sila ug eh empower to take charge of their own learning.” (IDI-14)

(Although there are times when they cannot meet the standards, we reinforce the need for them as board program students. In my case, I have taught criminology and teacher education, so it is essential to motivate and empower them to take charge of their own learning.)

Insights of the board program instructors with regards to the implementation of differentiated instruction and learner empowerment

There are five essential themes which are created based from the in-depth interviews of the participants on the first research question. Before the presentation of the results of the interviews and discussions, profiles of the participants for the qualitative collection are presented in table 1.2 The table represents the participants’ profiles for the qualitative selected purposively following the inclusion criteria: he or she must be a KCAST Instructor under the board programs namely; Institution of Teacher Education, Criminology and Agriculture with at least 2 years of teaching experience. Based on the table, the profiles are divided into participants’ program instructors.

Furthermore, Table 4.1 deals on the insights of the board program instructors in the implementation of differentiated instruction and learner empowerment. The essential themes which emerged from the transcriptions of the participants’ responses for the research question number one are consisted of overarching themes which are summarized in the said table.

Fostering Academic Success thru Personalized Learning and Differentiated Instruction. Prioritizing the needs of learners has a profound impact on the educational experience. By placing the focus on students' needs and preferences, instructors can create a supportive and inclusive learning environment where every individual feels valued and empowered. Moreover, instructors encourage to implements active engagement and participation, fostering a sense of ownership over one's learning journey. Additionally, prioritizing learners' needs enhances motivation and enthusiasm for learning process, as students feel that their interests and concerns are being acknowledged and addressed. Ultimately, by catering to the diverse needs of learners, educators can facilitate more meaningful and effective learning experiences, leading to improved academic outcomes and personal growth.

Differentiated Instruction and Personalized Learning. This is the first code for first probe issue. Many of the instructors under the institute of teacher education, criminology, and agriculture suggested that in the classroom, the significance of differentiated instruction in empowering learners cannot be underestimated.

Table 4.1. *The Insight of the Board Program Instructors with regards in implementing Differentiated Instruction and Learner Empowerment*

<i>Issue Probed</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>	<i>Code/ Categories</i>	<i>Essential Themes</i>	<i>Theoretical Support</i>
The Impact of Prioritizing the Needs of the Learners	The importance of having differentiated instruction to empower learners in the classroom. Utilizing different teaching approaches, strategies, and materials in the classroom. Identifying students’ needs, learning preferences, and learning styles. Recognizing students’ strengths and weaknesses. Fostering an engaging and effective learning environment to empower learners.	Differentiated Instruction and Personalized Learning Student-Centered Environment	Fostering Academic Success thru Personalized Learning and Differentiated Instruction	Social Cognitive Theory
Effect of Motivation to the Learning Interest of the Students	Fostering a comfortable learning environment towards the students’ learning experience. Needing guidance and support of the teacher as the facilitator of the learning process. Maintaining the attention of the students Impact of motivation on the learning experiences of the students. Effect of collaborative learning on the progress of the students. Maximizing students’ potential through engaging them in the learning process	Creative Supportive Learning Environment Motivation and Engagement	Cultivation of Optimal Learning Environment for Student Success	Self-Determination Theory
Implementation of Classroom Rules and Fostering Classroom Management	Needing to set rules in the classroom. Recognizing the individual differences inside the classroom. Having the authority to facilitate the learners’ learning. Having difficulties due to the diverse behavior of the students. Limited attention span of the students	Classroom Management and Instructional Leadership Classroom Dynamics and Challenges	Effective Teaching Practices for Student Engagement	Behaviorism Learning Theory
Effect of Seeking Advice from Colleagues or Co-instructors	Asking advice from co-workers regarding the implementation of differentiated instruction and learner empowerment. Seeking knowledge from peers and asking for help in selecting the best instructional activities tailored to specific students.	Professional Development and Collaboration	Collaborative Professional Growth for Effective Teaching	Social Constructivism Theory

Benefits on Attending Seminars, Workshops, and Trainings	Recognizing the benefit of seeking assistance through your co-instructors.	Professional Networking and Support		
	Establishing connections with people who have the same expertise.			
	Integrating differentiated activities, materials, and strategies in the classroom setting.	Classroom Instruction and Pedagogy		
	The need for attending webinars, trainings, and seminars in the context of teaching strategies.	Opportunities for Professional Development	Lifelong Learning and Professional Growth in Education	Experiential Learning Theory
	Recognizing the benefit of seminars and trainings in the teaching career.			
	Applying the strategies and skills learned through seminars and trainings.			
	Establishing learning as a continuous process.	Continuous Learning		
	Considering graduate schools to foster further learning that will help develop professional and personal aspects.			

Through utilizing various teaching approaches, strategies, and materials, instructors can cater the diverse needs and learning styles of students. This involves identifying individual students' needs, learning preferences, and unique learning styles to create tailored learning experiences. Through differentiated instruction, students are empowered to engage actively in their learning journey, as they receive personalized support and opportunities to succeed. By acknowledging and addressing the diverse needs of learners, educators cultivate an inclusive learning environment where every student feels valued and capable of achieving their full potential.

In connection, it is crucial to recognize the diversity of learning styles and preferences in the classroom, allowing the teacher to cater the different learning needs and modify various kind of instruction that connects with students on a deeper level will develop a better implementation of differentiated instruction and learner empowerment inside the classroom. As participant 1 stated that:

“It is crucial because you have to think that you have to plan and you have to know how to deliver this instruction so that your students will be empowered, your students would not be more engage in the classroom because the entire process, the entire outcomes depend on your implementation with this instruction so you have to think of it very well, you have to plan of it very well in order for the sake of the development of your students at the end of the day.” (IDI-01)

(It is crucial because you must consider, plan, and know how to deliver this instruction so that your students will be empowered. Your students will be more engaged in the classroom because the entire process and outcomes depend on your implementation of this instruction. Therefore, you must carefully consider and plan for the sake of your students' development at the end of the day.)

Additionally, Participant 1 recognizes that implementing differentiated instruction and learner empowerment is a crucial responsibility of the instructor, as they are the ones who facilitate the learning process of students. Through recognizing and catering to the diverse needs, abilities, and learning styles of each individual student, instructors can create an inclusive and engaging learning environment that maximizes the potential of every learner. He additionally stated that:

“So, there are other important jobs or responsibilities that we need to carry on or to undertake because we are not fulltime instructors, we have other task that we need to really accomplish so it is a complex task yung pag implement the integration of differentiated instruction and the promotion of learner empowerment is a complex task because it is a systematic.” (IDI-01)

(So, there are other important jobs or responsibilities that we need to carry out because we are not full-time instructors. We have other tasks that we really need to accomplish. Therefore, the implementation of differentiated instruction and the promotion of learner empowerment is a complex task. It involves a systematic process.)

Similarly, majority of the participants mentioned that utilizing different teaching approaches, strategies, and materials in the classroom at the same time identifying students’ needs, learning preferences, and learning styles is not an easy task. Instructors has a lot of things to put into consideration is personalizing instruction based on the learners need. As participant 5 stated that:

“Aside from the fact that we need to be flexible then it will somehow it is not so difficult if let say you are familiar already or you are master with that particular subject because less that occupation will be given or allotted to them but still, I find it difficult because aside from the facts that you be really give impart a lot of time during preparation.” (IDI-05)

(Aside from the fact that we need to be flexible, it may not be so difficult if, let us say, you are already familiar with or master a particular subject, as less occupation will be allotted to them. However, I still find it difficult because, besides the fact that you need to invest a lot of time during preparation.)

Student-Centered Environment. This is the second code for first probed issue. Recognizing students' strengths and weaknesses is

foundational to fostering an engaging and effective learning environment that empowers learners. By acknowledging individual strengths, educators can tailor instruction to capitalize on areas of proficiency, while also addressing weaknesses through targeted support and intervention. Creating an environment where students feel valued and understood encourages active participation and cultivates a sense of ownership over their learning journey.

In connection with that, differentiated instruction is essential in addressing individual differences among students to empower them, accommodating diverse learning styles and preferences and students learning needs. Thereby, providing each learner with opportunities to showcase their talents and engage effectively in the classroom will help them to be accountable to their own learning that will lead to empower them. As participant 3 stated that:

“That is the main purpose of having these differentiated instructions so that each of the learners having different intelligences and different learning styles and preferences have this what we called chance with in the classroom to parang make showcase or make use of their talents.” (IDI-03)

(That is the main purpose of having differentiated instructions, so that each of the learners with different intelligences and different learning styles and preferences has the chance within the classroom to showcase or make use of their talents.)

Additionally, as an instructor, it is essential to put commitment to the students' growth and development necessitates continuous learning, adaptation, and innovation. Through embracing differentiated instruction and staying open to change not only enhances the effectiveness of the teachers but also empowers the students to thrive in an increasingly complex and dynamic world. As participant 5 stated that:

“If you really committed to catering the needs of our students, we have to master differentiated learning by having this differentiated instruction, different strategies and approaches in teaching-learning process because you cannot empower your students if you yourself doesn't have any learning to the subject matter.” (IDI-05)

(If you are truly committed to meeting the needs of our students, we must excel in differentiated learning through various instructional methods, strategies, and approaches. This is because we cannot empower our students if we ourselves lack understanding of the subject matter.)

Cultivation of Optimal Learning Environment for Student Success. Motivation has a deep and multifaceted effect on students' learning interests. Motivation acts as a driving factor in shaping students' levels of engagement, persistence, and excitement for learning. Students who are motivated, whether intrinsically by their own personal interests and aspirations or extrinsically by external rewards or recognition, are more likely to actively participate in classroom activities, seek out difficult tasks, and demonstrate higher levels of effort and perseverance. In contrast, a lack of motivation can lead to disinterest, apathy, and poor academic achievement. As a result, promoting and maintaining students' motivation is critical for creating a positive learning environment in which they feel empowered, motivated, and eager to explore new knowledge and abilities.

Creative Supportive Learning Environment. This is the first code for the second probed issue. Majority of the participant suggested that in creating an inclusive, creative, and supportive learning environment, the teacher or instructor, as the facilitator, plays a crucial role in guiding and supporting students while ensuring their sustained attention throughout the learning process.

In connection with that, the faculty of KCAST board program shared their insight with regards to the critical importance of possessing a deep understanding of the subject matter as instructors to effectively implement differentiated learning strategies. This expertise enables educators to cater and modify the teaching approaches, skills, and techniques to the diverse needs of students, fostering a supportive and collaborative learning environment. As participant 5 stated that:

“I think one insight I can give is that as an instructors, we really must have the knowledge of our subject matter for us to differentiate our strategies, skills and techniques to our students, we can empower them by imparting our knowledge to them comprehensively and engaging as well.” (IDI-05)

(Therefore, I have come to realize that as instructors, it is crucial for us to possess a deep understanding of our subject matter. This knowledge allows us to effectively differentiate our teaching strategies, skills, and techniques to meet the diverse needs of our students. By doing so, we can empower them by providing comprehensive and engaging instruction.)

Moreover, prioritizing the implementation of differentiated instruction and learner empowerment is essential for cultivating an inclusive and effective learning environment that recognizes and caters the diverse student needs, fosters equity, and empowers students to take ownership of their learning journey, ultimately leading to enhanced academic achievement and the development of crucial lifelong skills. As participant 8 stated that:

“Now as this day, we are trying to know our students. Implementing differentiated instruction and learner empowerment is crucial for creating an inclusive and effective learning environment, overall, the combination of differentiated instruction and learner empowerment not only enhances academic achievement but also promotes a positive and inclusive classroom culture where every student can thrive.” (IDI-08)

(In today's educational context, the focus is on getting to know our students better. Implementing differentiated instruction and learner empowerment is crucial for establishing an inclusive and effective learning environment. Ultimately, the combination of differentiated instruction and learner empowerment not only enhances academic achievement but also fosters a positive and inclusive classroom culture where every student can thrive.)

Motivation and Engagement. This is the second code for the second probed issue. The impact of motivation on the learning experiences of students is profound, influencing their levels of engagement, persistence, and enthusiasm towards academic pursuits. Similarly, the effect of collaborative learning on the progress of students is significant, as it fosters peer interaction, cooperation, and communication skills, while also promoting critical thinking and problem-solving abilities through shared learning experiences.

In that sense, the instructors under board program courses recognize that it is important cultivate a motivational climate where students feel valued, challenged, and supported is crucial for nurturing their passion for learning and fostering academic success. Therefore, fostering and sustaining students' motivation is essential for creating a conducive learning environment where they feel empowered, inspired, and eager to explore new knowledge and skills. As participant 5 stated that:

“Importante jud nu nga you know well your students before ka mag introduce ug activity sa ilaha, ila ilahon nimo sila base sa ilang level kani sila naa ni sila sa above average, or average, or kani sila naa ni sila sa below average, once you manage your students well not just their thinking or not just their intelligences nu but you know personally, you know personal level you students mas dali sa imuha mag huna-huna ug activities para sa ilaha.” (IDI-05)

(It is really important to know your students well before introducing an activity to them. You need to understand them based on their level, whether they are above average, average, or below average. Once you manage your students well, not just their thinking or intelligence, but also on a personal level, it becomes easier for you to plan activities for them.)

Understanding the students enables instructors to modify their teaching methods while preserving classroom standards. This balance keeps students engaged and motivated while maintaining high standards of learning. By getting to know the students well, instructors can personalize their education to their specific needs and interests, creating a supportive learning atmosphere in which they feel valued and empowered. As participant 14 stated that:

“Primary man jud natu na client sa classroom is ang students so with that we must know our students well enough for us to be adjust or teaching approaches but also without compromising the standard that is being set in the classroom you have to be between the balance of knowing our students well and setting the standard to them as well so that they will be effective learners and educators in the future.” (IDI-14)

(Our primary clients in the classroom are the students, so we must know them well enough to adjust our teaching approaches without compromising the standards set in the classroom. We need to strike a balance between knowing our students well and maintaining those standards, so they become effective learners and educators in the future.)

Effective Teaching Practices for Student Engagement. In context of implementing differentiated instruction and learner empowerment, implementing classroom rules and fostering effective classroom management is crucial for creating a conducive learning environment tailored to the specific needs and dynamics of each classroom. This involves collaboratively establishing clear and positively framed rules that align with the school's values and the developmental stage of the students. Consistency, fairness, and clear communication of expectations are key in enforcing these rules, while building positive relationships with students helps cultivate a sense of trust and mutual respect. Recognizing and addressing individual needs through flexibility and adaptation ensures that all students feel supported and included.

Classroom Management and Instructional Leadership. This the first code for the third probe issue. Many of the participant share their insight with regards in setting rules is imperative to establish a structured environment conducive to learning. These rules provide clear expectations and boundaries for students, fostering a sense of safety and order. Moreover, recognizing the individual differences among students is essential for effective teaching and learning. As the facilitator of learning, the teacher holds the authority to create and maintain this environment, guiding students through their educational journey by providing direction, support, and opportunities for growth.

In connection to that, instructors under board programs realize that teacher or instructors has a pivotal role in managing the classroom environment. This understanding emphasizes the importance of flexibility in the teacher's approach, particularly in giving instructions. The teacher recognizes the diverse needs and backgrounds of students, highlighting the necessity to consider all aspects when delivering instructions and managing the classroom. As participant 4 stated that:

“Akong gina instill sa akong mind na whatever will be the outcome inside the classroom naga depende na siya sa akoa so ako mismo as a teacher dapat ko maging flexible, dapat ko maging flexible in terms of giving instructions dili lang kay mu focus lang ko sa isa ka aspect but then eh consider pud nako ang tanang aspect since lahi-lahi man ug panginahanglan ang students inside sa classroom.” (IDI-04)

(I always remind myself that whatever the outcome in the classroom is, it depends on me. So, as a teacher, I need to be flexible. I should

be flexible in terms of giving instructions, not just focusing on one aspect, but considering all aspects. Since students in the classroom have different needs.)

Moreover, in order to effectively facilitate learning, it is essential to establish clear rules, learning outcomes, and grading systems from the beginning, conduct diagnostic tests to identify student needs, build strong relationships with students through authentic communication, and maintain flexibility in teaching approaches to ensure continual improvement for both students and instructors in the 21st century classroom. As participant 8 stated that:

“First is kailangan man jud mag set ug rules ug mag set ug outcomes on what are the expected learning of the students so dapat naka set na gyud ng outline, outcomes, grading system in the very beginning of the class.” (IDI-08)

(Firstly, it is crucial to establish rules and set learning outcomes for students, outlining the grading system at the beginning of the class.)

Additionally, effective teaching relies heavily on both communication skills and classroom management skills. Communication skills are vital for clearly articulating expectations and instructions to students, as any lack of clarity can lead to confusion and hinder their ability to engage in activities. Teachers must be able to express themselves clearly, concisely, and in a manner that is easily understood by their students. As participant 7 stated that:

“So communication skills are very critical because if you do not have the knowledge about communication skills well you will encourage more confusion to your students if dili nimo ma communicate ug tarong ang imong expectation ang imong instructions to them magpataka rana imong students buhat ug activity.” (IDI-07)

(So communication skills are very critical because if you don't have knowledge about communication skills, you will encourage more confusion among your students. If you can't communicate your expectations and instructions clearly to them, your students will just end up doing the activities haphazardly.)

Classroom Dynamics and Challenges. This is the second code for the third probe issue. Many of the participant shared their insight with regards in facing challenges arising from the diverse behaviors of students and coping with their limited attention spans. Navigating the classroom environment is challenging due to the diverse range of behaviors observed by students.

In connection, teacher's primary role is to educate students, it's essential to consider factors like their abilities, knowledge, learning styles, and emotions. Differentiated instruction acknowledges the individuality of students, recognizing that there's no one-size-fits-all approach to teaching. Flexibility and adaptability in teaching methods are necessary to meet the diverse needs of students effectively. As participant 13 stated that:

“As a teacher it is not only your role is to teach the students but it is primarily that is your job to teach the students or the learners however it will not end there you need to consider so many things just like their abilities, knowledge, types and also if the students are involving emotions you need to be considerate as well when it comes to dealing with these students because it can affect as well their learning.” (IDI-13)

(As a teacher, your role is not only to impart knowledge but primarily to educate students or learners. However, it does not end there, you must also consider various factors such as their abilities, prior knowledge, learning styles, and even their emotional involvement. When dealing with students, it's important to be considerate of their emotions as it can impact their learning.)

Collaborative Professional Growth for Effective Teaching. In context of implementing differentiated instruction and learner empowerment seeking advice from colleagues or co-instructors can have a profound effect on a teacher's professional growth and classroom management. By engaging in collaborative discussions and sharing experiences, teachers can gain valuable insights, perspectives, and innovative ideas that can enhance their teaching methods and classroom management strategies. Learning from the experiences of others allows teachers to expand their repertoire of effective instructional techniques, address challenges more creatively, and adapt their approaches to better meet the diverse needs of their students. Additionally, seeking advice fosters a sense of camaraderie and support among educators, creating a collaborative learning environment where continuous improvement and professional development are prioritized.

Professional Development and Collaboration. This is the first code for the fourth probe issue. This collaborative approach not only helps teachers stay up-to-date with the latest educational trends but also fosters a supportive and dynamic learning environment for both teachers and students. When teachers work together to implement differentiated instruction, they can better cater to the diverse needs of their learners, ensuring that each student is empowered to reach their full potential.

Collaborating with colleagues is a powerful tool for educators to enhance their teaching practices and better serve the diverse needs of their students. By engaging in meaningful discussions and sharing ideas, educators can learn from each other's experiences, gain new perspectives, and develop innovative strategies to create inclusive and engaging learning environments. As participant 3 stated that:

“Asking your colleagues or asking someone who is expert to that field that could be one thing that you can consider also if you are too shy to ask someone as you as you know that you are not good enough to that particular area should consider reading materials or attending to conferences or workshop so that it could be the avenue to improve yourself in conducting activities or instructions in a

particular class setting.” (IDI-03)

(Asking your colleagues or seeking guidance from experts in the field is one option to consider if you feel hesitant to admit your shortcomings in a particular area. Alternatively, you can enhance your skills by reading materials, attending conferences, or workshops related to that topic.)

Moreover, seeking knowledge from peers and asking for assistance in selecting instructional activities tailored to individual students can lead to more personalized and engaging learning experiences. Through this collaborative approach, teachers can gain valuable insights, refine their teaching practices, and ultimately create a supportive learning environment conducive to student success. As participant 4 stated that:

“Okay maybe I can suggest na ano, do not settle for less and also do not hesitate to ask some advice, guidance to your peers, to the heads and so on, kasi once you are open to them maybe matabangan jud ka nila at the same time ma advisan pud ka ug tama ug ang dapat himuon pud.” (IDI-04)

(Okay, perhaps I can suggest not to settle for less and also not to hesitate to seek advice and guidance from your peers, supervisors, and others. Because once you are open to them, they may be able to help you, and at the same time, they can advise you on what needs to be done correctly.)

Professional Networking and Support. This is the second code for the fourth probe issue. Recognizing the benefit of seeking assistance through your co-instructors can greatly enhance your professional development as an educator. By establishing connections with colleagues who possess similar expertise, you can leverage their insights, experiences, and knowledge to improve your teaching practices.

Collaborating with co-instructors allows for the exchange of ideas, strategies, and resources, fostering a supportive learning community where educators can learn from each other and collectively strive for excellence in the classroom. Moreover, the exchange of knowledge and the collective effort to strive for excellence in the classroom can lead to personal and professional growth for the educators involved, ultimately benefiting the entire educational community. As participant 5 stated that:

“Collaboration I guess... in collaboration we seek assistant not only to the submit yourself to the training’s collaboration is with asking help with your co-instructors or teachers it is one way of enhancing your skills, to broaden your knowledge because through that you can will be able to learn to your fellow instructors it could be it is one way or best way, also to cope up with the challenges you’ve encounter in implementing differentiated instruction and learner empowerment.” (IDI-05)

(Collaboration, I guess, is crucial. In collaboration, we seek assistance not only by participating in training but also by asking for help from co-instructors or teachers. It is a way to enhance your skills and broaden your knowledge because you can learn from your fellow instructors. It is also one of the best ways to cope with the challenges encountered in implementing differentiated instruction and empowering learners.)

Similarly, the importance of being open to learning and seeking assistance from colleagues in the teaching profession is crucial in the teaching career. It emphasizes that asking for help is not a sign of weakness but rather a means of continuous growth and improvement. Additionally, it highlights the value of balancing independent learning with seeking guidance from others, demonstrating initiative and resourcefulness while also benefiting from the knowledge and experience of more seasoned educators. As participant 7 stated that:

“My suggestions is you have to be open to ideas you may ask help to your fellow instructors there is no harm in asking wala jud, dili jud natu ika ulaw nu nga mangutana kay miskan katung mga brightest nga neophyte teachers na akong kaila mangutana gyud gihapon sila. So in order to expand your knowledge in your teaching career you need to solicit idea to your co-teachers who have a lot of experience and expertise than you.” (IDI-07)

(My suggestion is to be open to ideas and ask for help from your fellow instructors. There is no harm in asking; there is nothing to be ashamed of when you ask questions because even the brightest neophyte teachers whom I know still ask questions. To expand your knowledge in your teaching career, you need to solicit ideas from your co-teachers who have more experience and expertise than you.)

Additionally, to effectively address challenges or overcome problems in teaching, seeking support from peers and experts is essential. If you feel overwhelmed and unable to handle the situation alone, it's beneficial to seek advice from experienced teachers or advisors. They can provide valuable insights and information to help you strategize your lessons more effectively. As participant 13 additionally stated that:

“Okay to effectively face some challenges or to overcome this problem you need some peers you need some experts if you think that you cannot do it alone try to seek advice from those who are already seasoned teachers, advisers, you can ask some information that will help you strategize your lesson.” (IDI-13)

(To effectively tackle challenges or overcome problems, you need the support of peers and experts. If you feel unable to handle a situation alone, seek advice from seasoned teachers or advisors. They can offer valuable insights and information to help you plan your lessons more effectively.)

Lifelong Learning and Professional Growth in Education. In context of differentiated instruction and learner empowerment instructors under board programs shared their insight related to attending seminars, workshops, and training sessions that offers numerous benefits for professional growth and development in the field of education. Instructors believed that by participating in these kinds of activities, educators can stay updated on the latest trends, methodologies, and technologies relevant to their field. Moreover, seminars, workshops, and trainings often feature expert speakers and facilitators who offer valuable insights and practical strategies that educators can implement in their teaching practice.

Opportunities for Professional Development. This is the first code for the fifth probe issue. Many of the participant shared their insights with regards to the realm of teaching strategies, they believed that there is a growing recognition of the necessity for educators to attend webinars, trainings, and seminars. These activities will provide invaluable opportunities for teachers to stay abreast of emerging pedagogical approaches, technological advancements, and innovative teaching methods.

Participating in professional development events, such as conferences, webinars, trainings, and seminars, allows educators to expand their knowledge and hone their teaching skills. These opportunities enable them to explore a wide range of teaching methodologies and techniques tailored to diverse learning styles, ensuring that they can create inclusive and engaging learning environments for students of all backgrounds and abilities. As participant 2 stated that:

“For me about sa instructors, dapat they will sent into teacher faculty development trainings on how to implement different teaching strategies... your expertise in this field so you must be send to that trainings so that after you will be equipped you have the knowledge and of course ma share jud sa mga studyante, actually your training will not address to the school but your training will be address to your student.” (IDI-02)

(For me, regarding instructors, they should be sent to teacher faculty development trainings on how to implement various teaching strategies. As an expert in this field, you must attend these trainings so that you can be equipped with the necessary knowledge to share with your students. Actually, your training is not just for the benefit of the school but also directly benefits your students.)

Moreover, the importance of continuous learning and adaptation in the field of education emphasizes that the need for educators to remain open-minded and receptive to change, especially concerning evolving teaching strategies and trends. Additionally, it highlights the proactive approach of seeking professional development opportunities such as trainings, seminars, and engagement in various activities to enhance instructional practices. As participant 3 suggested that:

“We should always be involved in different professional and personal trainings and seminars because as the time goes by there will always be new trend in the teaching strategies... we will get ourselves to some trainings, exposures, different engagements or extension activities that will give us the inputs or knowledge regarding on how to improve our instructions at the same time teaching strategy.” (IDI-03)

(We should always be involved in various professional and personal trainings and seminars because new trends in teaching strategies continually emerge. By participating in these trainings, exposures, engagements, and extension activities, we gain valuable inputs and knowledge on how to improve our instruction and teaching strategies.)

Additionally, instructors must consistently be prepared to confront challenges in implementing differentiated instruction and learner empowerment, while also demonstrating flexibility to adapt to changes and new teaching approaches, emphasizing the importance of engaging in seminars and trainings. As participant additionally 7 stated that:

“Also engage yourself in seminar and trainings even though you are an instructor you still need to fuel yourself the knowledge that is highly important in your teaching career and one of the way is that engaging yourself in seminars or training just like in education we have PAFTE which taught us or give us the inputs about teaching strategies that will surely help us in implementing differentiated instruction as well as to empower learner.” (IDI-07)

(“Additionally, they should engage in seminars and trainings to continually enhance their knowledge, even though they are already instructors. These opportunities, such as those provided by organizations like PAFTE, offer valuable insights into teaching strategies that can effectively implement differentiated instruction and empower learners.”)

Continuous Learning. This is the second code for the fifth probe issue. Many of the participant suggested that educators should prioritize continuous growth and development in both their professional and personal capacities. Through graduate education, educators aim to delve deeper into their field, explore new perspectives, and acquire specialized expertise that enhances their effectiveness in teaching and empowers their overall growth and development. As participant 9 stated that:

“First, continuous Learning and Professional Development, Instructors must stay informed about current best practices, research, and strategies related to differentiated instruction and learner empowerment... engage in ongoing professional development opportunities, such as workshops, conferences, and courses, to enhance your knowledge and skills in these areas.” (IDI-09)

(First, continuous learning and professional development, instructors must be updated on the latest best practices, research, and strategies concerning differentiated instruction and learner empowerment. Engage in ongoing professional development opportunities, such as workshops, conferences, and courses, to improve your knowledge and skills in these areas.)

Similarly, considering the evolving needs of 21st-century learners and the technological advancements, educators, especially those from previous generations, should actively engage in seminars, training, and collaborative practices, such as peer tutoring and observation, to better implement differentiated instruction and empower learners in the classroom, addressing the challenges posed by the changing educational landscape. As participant 10 stated that:

“Strategies are evolving as well considering that our generations are evolving as well this generation has it is specific needs also for example the students ten years ago is far different from the students that we have now as what I have said we have 21st century learners example there has this issues in critical thinking ability, collaboration if you wanted to address this things you also have to submit yourself to trainings and seminars as a teacher.” (IDI-10)

(Strategies are continuously evolving to meet the specific needs of today's 21st-century learners, particularly regarding critical thinking and collaboration skills. To address these challenges, educators must actively participate in training and seminars to enhance their instructional methods, especially considering the technological advancements that have created a gap between previous and current generations of teachers.)

Additionally, fostering a culture of collaboration and open communication allows instructors to learn from one another's experiences and discover successful strategies that work in their specific contexts. When faculty actively participate in sharing best practices, it strengthens relationships, promotes innovation, and ultimately benefits student learning outcomes. Institutions should prioritize creating opportunities for faculty to connect, such as through professional learning communities, collaborative projects, and social events, to facilitate the exchange of ideas and resources. Participant 14 suggested that:

“So with that what I can share to my fellow instructors if you have difficulties in your teaching and even in the implementation of differentiated instruction and learner empowerment just like I did you just need to seek advice from your peers or mentors in the institution.” (IDI-14)

(Therefore, what I can advise my fellow instructors, if they encounter challenges in teaching or implementing differentiated instruction and learner empowerment, is to seek guidance from their peers or mentors within the institution.)

Data Integration of the Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

The present study on the differentiated instruction and learner empowerment among the faculty of KCAST Board Programs in a local college carries out a mixed methods approach employing convergent parallel approach. The third research question of the study involves the corroboration of the findings from quantitative and qualitative phase. The table 4.2 on the salient quantitative and qualitative findings presents the focal points in the first column which contains the aspect or focal points of the study followed by the quantitative and qualitative findings in the second and third column. The findings from the quantitative phase are usually the indicators with the highest mean while the qualitative findings which display the identified responses show confirmation or disconfirmation to the quantitative results.

Table 4.2. Joint Display of Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

<i>Aspect Or Focal Point</i>	<i>Quantitative Findings</i>	<i>Qualitative Findings</i>	<i>Nature Of Data Integration</i>	<i>Axiological Implications</i>
Differentiated Instruction	From Table 2.1 on Lesson Design and Implementation with an overall mean of 4.69, specifically item 1 which is about designing a lesson that engages students as members of the learning process (M=4.79), which are all rated as very high.	On table 3.2 on engagement and collaboration in collaborative learning for inclusive engagement specifically core idea 2 which is about engaging students in group activities and collaborative tasks to enhance learning experiences.	Merging – converging	High quantitative ratings, along with qualitative findings, suggest a strong focus on inclusive engagement strategies, emphasizing collaborative learning environments and support for diverse learning needs.
	From Table 2.1 on Content with an overall mean of 4.82 specifically item 4 which is about promoting individualized instruction as much (M=4.71), which are all rated as very high.	On table 3.2 under the essential theme of recognition and accommodation of student diversity to enhance pedagogy specifically in the category of recognition of students diversity, core idea 1 which is about recognizing the different learner styles of the students and their different intelligences.	Merging- Converging	The convergence of quantitative data promoting individualized instruction and regular assessment, along with qualitative findings recognizing diverse learner styles and intelligences, highlights the value of personalized learning pathways and inclusivity in education.
	From table 2.1 on Procedures with an overall mean of 4.66, item 2 which is about promoting cooperative learning	On table 3.2 under the essential theme of recognition and accommodation of student diversity to enhance pedagogy	Merging- converging	The convergence of high quantitative ratings in promoting cooperative learning with differentiated instruction,

	by having differentiated instruction (M=4.77) which are all rated as very high.	specifically in the category of differentiated instruction, core idea 2 enhancing the learning process of the students by having differentiated instruction.		along with qualitative recognition of its role in enhancing diverse student learning, emphasizes the value of inclusive pedagogical approaches cater individual needs.
	From table 2.1 on Communication with an overall mean of 4.81, item 1 which is all about asking my students during my discussion to trigger divergent modes of thinking (M=4.76), which are all rated as very high.	On table 4.1 under the essential theme cultivation of optimal learning environment for student success specifically in the category of creative supportive learning environment, core idea 1 which is about fostering a comfortable learning environment towards the students' learning experience.	Merging-converging	The convergence of high quantitative ratings in encouraging divergent thinking during discussions, along with qualitative emphasis on fostering a comfortable learning environment for students' experiences, highlights the value of creating supportive and creative atmospheres to enhance student success.
	From table 2.1 on Learning with an overall mean of 4.76, item 3 which is about assessing regularly to know what my students already know and what are the things they need to know (M=4.84), which are all rated as very high.	On table 4.1 under the essential theme effective teaching practices for student engagement specifically in the category of classroom management and instructional leadership, core idea 3 which is about having the authority to facilitate the learners' learning.	Merging-Converging	The high quantitative ratings in regular assessment with qualitative emphasis on instructional leadership, where teachers have the authority to facilitate learning, emphasize the importance of proactive teaching practices that empower students to engage effectively in their learning journey.
Learner Empowerment	From table 2.2 under Impact with an overall mean of 4.80, item 5 which is about encouraging students to contribute to the learning of others in the class (M=4.85) which are all rated as very high	On table 3.2 under the essential theme collaborative learning for inclusive, category of engagement and collaboration in collaborative learning for inclusive engagement, core idea 4 which is promoting active engagement through effectively working with teams and collaborating towards common goals.	Merging – converging	The convergence of high quantitative ratings in student contributions with qualitative emphasis on collaborative engagement underscores the value of teamwork and collaboration in inclusive learning environments.
	From table 2.2 under Meaningfulness with an overall mean of 4.80, item 1 which is about expressing genuine appreciation to my students when they participate actively in the class (M=4.87) and item 3 which is about considering the task I have required in my class to be valuable to my students (M4.79), which are rated as very high.	On table 4.1 under the essential theme cultivation of optimal learning environment for student success specifically, in the category of creative supportive learning environment, core idea 1 which is about fostering a comfortable learning environment towards the students' learning experience.	Merging-converging	The high quantitative ratings for appreciating student participation, coupled with qualitative focus on fostering a comfortable learning environment, highlight the importance of supportive settings for student success.
	From table 2.2 under competence with an overall mean of 4.81, item 1 which is about believing in my capabilities to achieve empowering learner in the class (M=4.81), and item 5 which is about feeling very competent in empowering students in their learning	On the table 4.1 under the essential theme effective teaching practices for student engagement specifically, in the category classroom management and instructional leadership, core idea 3 which is about having the authority to facilitate the learners' learning.	Merging-Converging	High ratings for believing in one's teaching abilities and feeling competent in empowering students, along with emphasis on instructional leadership, highlight the importance of facilitating learning effectively.

<p>Lived Experiences and Strategies of the Board Program instructor in implementing differentiated instruction and learner empowerment.</p>	<p>process (M= 4.80), which are rated as very high. From the table 2.1 under the indicator Lesson design and Implementation item 5 which is about using multisensory teaching approaches (M=4.69), and under the indicator Procedures item 4 which is about matching my teaching practices to the needs of the students (M=4.79), which are rated as very high.</p>	<p>On the table 3.2 under the essential theme recognition and accommodation of student diversity to enhance pedagogy specifically in the category of differentiated instruction, core idea 1 which is about fostering differentiated instructions to cater to the different learning styles and preferences of the students.</p>	<p>Merging-converging</p>	<p>The Board Program instructor's commitment to implementing differentiated instruction and learner empowerment is evident in high ratings for using multisensory teaching approaches and matching teaching practices to student needs, aligning with a qualitative focus on fostering instruction tailored to diverse learning styles and preferences.</p>
	<p>From table 2.1 under the indicator Content item 2 which is about crafting my lessons to promote coherent conceptual understanding (M= 4.87), item 3 utilizing solid grasp of the subject matter content inherent in the lessons (M= 4.85), and under indicator Procedure item 1 which is about creating a PowerPoint presentation to serve as a resource for students' notes (M=4.85), which are all rated as very high</p>	<p>On table 3.2 under the essential theme equity and inclusion in education specifically in the category of creating an inclusive classroom environment, core idea 2 which is about needing various strategies and teaching approaches in enhancing learning experiences of the diverse students.</p>	<p>Merging-converging</p>	<p>High ratings for crafting lessons to promote conceptual understanding, utilizing subject matter expertise, and creating resources like PowerPoint presentations, converge with a qualitative focus on employing diverse teaching strategies to enhance learning experiences for a diverse student body, highlighting a commitment to inclusive education that values equity and inclusion.</p>
	<p>From table 2.1 under the indicator Communication item 4 which about encouraging students to respect each other and their opinions (M=4.91), item 5 which is about believing that students should have voice in my classroom (M=4.92), and under the indicator Learning item 5 which is about acting as the resource person, working to support and enhance students learning (M=4.88), which are all rated as very high</p>	<p>On the table 3.2 under the essential theme recognition and accommodation of student's diversity to enhance pedagogy specifically in the category of recognition of student diversity, core idea 2 which is about understanding the diversity of each student in the classroom.</p>	<p>Merging-converging</p>	<p>High ratings for encouraging respect among students, valuing student voices, and acting as a supportive resource in learning, converge with a qualitative focus on understanding the diversity of each student in the classroom, indicating a commitment to cultivating an optimal learning environment that recognizes and accommodates student diversity for enhanced pedagogy.</p>
	<p>From table 2.2 under the indicator of Impact item 3 which is about utilizing alternative approaches to learning to encourage the class (M=4.80), and under indicator Impact item 2 which is about requiring personally meaningful task that hold personal significance towards my students (M=4.79), which are all rated as very high.</p>	<p>On the table 3.2 under the essential theme equity and inclusion in education specifically in the category of understanding students' needs and preferences, core idea 1 which is about having difficulties in catering individual needs through not knowing the students' learning styles and preferences.</p>	<p>Merging-converging</p>	<p>High ratings for utilizing alternative learning approaches and requiring personally meaningful tasks for students converge with a qualitative focus on understanding students' needs and preferences, indicating a commitment to equity and inclusion by addressing individual learning styles and preferences for enhanced educational outcomes.</p>
	<p>From table 2.2 under the indicator competence item 2 which is about possessing the necessary skills to empower learners (M=4.81), and item studying the lesson before having my session in class (M=75), which are all rated as very high.</p>	<p>On the table 3.2 under the essential theme recognition and accommodation of student's diversity to enhance pedagogy, specifically in the category of improvement of teaching-learning process, core idea 1 which is identifying applicable strategies and approaches to</p>	<p>Merging-converging</p>	<p>High ratings for possessing necessary skills to empower learners and studying lessons before class sessions converge with a qualitative focus on improving the teaching-learning process by identifying applicable strategies and approaches to cater to diverse</p>

		cater the diverse students inside the classroom.		students in the classroom, highlighting a commitment to enhancing pedagogy through recognition and accommodation of student diversity.
	From table 2.1 under the indicator Content item 4 which is about utilizing solid grasp of the subject matter content inherent in the lesson (M=4.85), and under the indicator procedure item 5 which is about instructing my students to take notes when I am lecturing (M=4.51), which are all rated as very high.	On the table 4.1 under the essential theme fostering academic success thru personalized learning and differentiated instruction specifically in the category of differentiated instruction and personalized learning, core idea 1 which is about the importance of having differentiated instruction to empower learners in the classroom.	Merging-converging	High ratings for utilizing a solid grasp of subject matter content and a qualitative focus on differentiated instruction and personalized learning converge, emphasizing the importance of employing differentiated instruction to empower learners in the classroom for fostering academic success.
	From table 2.1 under the indicator communication item 2 which is about using differentiated instruction in my lessons' activities (M=.69), and item 4 which is about encouraging students to respect each other and their opinion (M=4.91), which are all rated as very high.	On the table 4.1 under the essential theme cultivation of optimal learning environment for students' success specifically in the code creative supportive learning environment, core idea 1 which is about fostering a comfortable learning environment towards the students' learning experience.	Merging-converging	High ratings for using differentiated instruction and encouraging respect among students converge with a qualitative focus on fostering a comfortable learning environment, highlighting the importance of creating a supportive atmosphere for students' learning experiences in the pursuit of optimal learning environments and student success.
	From table 2.2 under the indicator Impact item 2 which is about choosing the methods I can use to perform my work (M=4.81), and item 4 which is about making an impact on the way things run in my class (M=4.75), which are all rated as very high.	On the table 4.1 under the essential theme effective teaching practices for student engagement specifically in the category of classroom management and instructional leadership, core idea 3 which is about having the authority to facilitate the learners' learning.	Merging-converging	High ratings for choosing methods and making an impact in the classroom converge with a qualitative emphasis on instructional leadership, highlighting the importance of having authority to facilitate student learning effectively in classroom management practices for student engagement.
	From table 2.2 under the indicator Meaningfulness item 3 which is about considering the task I have required in my class to be valuable to my students (M= 4.79), and under the indicator Competence item 4 which is about building confidence in my ability to successfully perform the task in the class (M=4.87), which are all rated as very high.	On the table 4.1 under the essential theme cultivation of optimal learning environment for students' success specifically in the category off creative supportive learning environment, core idea 1 which is about fostering a comfortable learning environment towards the students' learning experience.	Merging-converging	High ratings for valuing tasks and building confidence converge with a focus on fostering a supportive, creative learning environment, emphasizing its importance for student success.
Insights of the Board Program Instructors with regards in implementing Differentiated Instruction and Learner Empowerment	From table 2.1 under the indicator Content item 4 which is about utilizing solid grasp of the subject matter content inherent in the lesson (M=4.85), and under the indicator Procedure item 5 which is about instructing my students to take notes when I am lecturing (M=4.51), which	On the table 4.1 under the essential theme fostering academic success personalized thru learning and differentiated instruction specifically in the category differentiated instruction personalized of and learning, core idea 1 which is about importance having differentiated instruction to	Merging-converging	High ratings for utilizing a solid grasp of subject matter content and a qualitative focus differentiated instruction and personalized learning converge, emphasizing the importance employing differentiated instruction empower of on to learners in the classroom for fostering

are all rated as very high.	empower learners in the classroom.		academic success.
From table 2.1 under indicator the communication item 2 which is about using differentiated instruction in my lessons' activities (M=.69), and item 4 which is about encouraging students respect to each other and their opinion (M=4.91), which are all rated as very high.	On the table 4.1 under essential cultivation the theme of optimal learning environment for students' success specifically in the code creative supportive learning environment, core idea 1 which is about fostering a comfortable learning environment towards the students' learning experience.	Merging-converging	High ratings for using differentiated instruction and encouraging respect among students converge with a qualitative focus on fostering a comfortable learning environment, highlighting the importance creating supportive of a atmosphere for students' learning experiences in the pursuit of optimal learning environments and student success.
From table 2.2 under the indicator Impact item 2 which is about choosing the methods I can use to perform my work (M=4.81), and item 4 which is about making an impact on the way things run in my class (M=4.75), which are all rated as very high.	On the table 4.1 under essential the theme effective teaching practices student engagement specifically in the category classroom of management and instructional leadership, core idea 3 which is about having the authority to facilitate the learners learning.	Merging-converging	High ratings for choosing methods making and an impact in the classroom converge with a qualitative emphasis instructional leadership, highlighting the importance of having authority to facilitate student learning effectively in classroom management practices for students' engagement.
From table 2.2 under the indicator Impact item 2 which is about choosing the methods I can use to perform my work (M=4.81), and item 4 which is about making an impact on the way things run in my class (M=4.75), which are all rated as very high.	On the table 4.1 under essential the theme effective teaching practices for student engagement specifically in the category of classroom management and instructional leadership, core idea 3 which is about having the authority facilitate learners' learning.	Merging-converging	High ratings for choosing methods and making an impact in the classroom converge with the qualitative result, emphasis on instructional leadership, highlighting the importance of having authority to facilitate student learning effectively in classroom management practices for student engagement.
From table 2.2 under indicator the Meaningfulness item 3 which is about considering the task have required in my class to be valuable to my students (M= 4.79), and under the indicator Competence item 4 which is about building confidence in my ability successfully to perform the task in the class (M=4.87), which are all rated as very high.	On the table 4.1 under the essential theme cultivation of optimal learning environment for students' success specifically in the category of creative supportive learning environment, core idea 1 which is about fostering a comfortable learning environment towards the students' learning experience.	Merging-converging	High ratings for valuing tasks and building confidence converge with focus fostering a supportive, creative learning environment, emphasizing its importance for student success

Differentiated Instruction

In the quantitative phase under the indicator of lesson design and implementation, the specific item 1 was rated very high by the participants, designing a lesson that engages students as members of the learning process. The result is connected with the qualitative findings, which categorized as engagement and collaboration in collaborative learning for inclusive engagement, specifically in the core idea engaging students in group activities and collaborative tasks to enhance learning experiences. Hence, very high quantitative ratings and qualitative findings indicate a strong emphasis on inclusive engagement strategies, particularly through collaborative learning environments and tailored support for diverse learning needs. It is safe then to say that the quantitative results merge the qualitative result.

In the quantitative phase under the indicator content, rated as very high by the respondents, specifically item about promoting individualized instruction as much as possible. This result is connected with the qualitative result categorized as recognition of student's diversity in the core idea, recognizing the different learner styles of the students and their different intelligences, under the theme,

recognition and accommodation of student's diversity to enhance pedagogy. The integration of quantitative data emphasizing individualized instruction and ongoing assessment, combined with qualitative insights acknowledging diverse learner styles and intelligences, put emphasis on the importance of personalized learning pathways and inclusivity in education. Hence, this can be viewed that quantitative merges with the qualitative results. In the quantitative phase under the indicator procedures, rated as very high by the respondents, specifically item promoting cooperative learning by having differentiated instruction. The result is connected with the qualitative results particularly categorize as differentiated instruction, under the core idea, enhancing the learning process of the students by having differentiated instruction. Thus, the combination of strong quantitative ratings supporting cooperative learning alongside differentiated instruction, along with qualitative recognition of their positive impact on diverse student learning, underscores the value of inclusive pedagogical approaches that cater to individual needs. This means that quantitative merges with the qualitative results.

In the quantitative phase under the indicator communication, rated as very high by the respondents, specifically item asking my students during my discussion to trigger divergent modes of thinking. The result is connected with the qualitative result under the category creative supportive learning environment, specifically core idea, fostering a comfortable learning environment towards the students learning experience. This means that the alignment of high quantitative ratings in promoting divergent thinking during discussions, coupled with qualitative emphasis on cultivating a comfortable learning environment that values students' experiences, highlights the importance of fostering supportive and creative atmospheres to enhance student success. Therefore, quantitative merges with the qualitative results.

In the quantitative phase under the indicator learning, rated as very high by the respondents, specifically item assessing regularly to know what my students already know and what are the things they need to know. The result is connected with the qualitative findings categorize as, classroom management and instructional leadership specifically under the core idea having the authority to facilitate the learners' learning. This implies that the high quantitative ratings in regular assessment, along with qualitative emphasis on instructional leadership where teachers facilitate learning, highlight the importance of proactive teaching practices that empower students to effectively engage in their learning journey. This means, quantitative merges with the qualitative results.

Learner Empowerment

In the quantitative phase under the indicator impact, rated as very high by the participants, specifically item about encouraging students to contribute to the learning of others in the class. The result is connected with the qualitative findings categorize as engagement and collaboration in collaborative learning for inclusive engagement specifically under the core idea promoting active engagement through effectively working with teams and collaborating towards common goals. This means that high quantitative ratings in student contributions, alongside qualitative emphasis on collaborative engagement, emphasizes the value of teamwork and collaboration in fostering inclusive learning environments. Hence, quantitative merges with the qualitative results.

In the quantitative phase under the indicator meaningfulness, rated as very high by the participants specifically items expressing genuine appreciation to my students when they participate actively in the class and considering the task I have required in my class to be valuable to my students. The result is connected with the qualitative findings categorize as creative supportive learning environment under the core idea fostering a comfortable learning environment towards the students' learning experience. This means that the high quantitative ratings for appreciating student participation, combined with a qualitative focus on fostering a comfortable learning environment, underscore the importance of supportive settings for student success. Therefore, quantitative merges with the qualitative results.

In the quantitative phase of the study, respondents rated their competence as very high, particularly in believing in their capabilities to empower learners and feeling competent in guiding students through the learning process. This finding aligns with the qualitative results, where themes of classroom management and instructional leadership emphasized teachers' authority to facilitate effective learning. The connection between these quantitative and qualitative insights underscores the importance of teacher competence in creating an empowering learning environment. When teachers are confident in their abilities and feel competent in their roles, they are better equipped to implement instructional leadership strategies that foster meaningful student engagement and success. Thus, the merging of quantitative and qualitative results highlights the critical role of teacher competence in facilitating both student empowerment and overall academic achievement.

Lived Experiences and Strategies of the Board Program Instructor in Implementing Differentiated Instruction and Learner Empowerment

In the quantitative findings under the indicator lesson design and implementation, rated as very high by the respondents specifically item using multisensory teaching approaches and under the indicator procedures also rated as very high by the participants, item matching my teaching practices to the needs of the students. The results in connected with the qualitative findings categorize as differentiated instruction under the core idea fostering differentiated instructions to cater to the different learning styles and preferences of the students. With that, the commitment of the Board Program instructor to implementing differentiated instruction and learner empowerment is demonstrated through high ratings for using multisensory teaching approaches and aligning teaching practices with student needs, reflecting a qualitative emphasis on tailoring instruction to diverse learning styles and preferences. This means that qualitative and quantitative merges.

Moreover, in the quantitative findings under the indicator content, item crafting my lessons to promote coherent conceptual understanding and indicator procedures item creating a PowerPoint presentation to serve as a resource for students' notes which are all rated as very high which means that these findings were always manifested by the respondents. The results are connected to the qualitative results categorize as creating an inclusive classroom environment under the core idea needing various strategies and teaching approaches in enhancing learning experiences of the diverse students. This implies that the high ratings for crafting lessons to promote conceptual understanding, utilizing subject matter expertise, and creating resources like PowerPoint presentations, align with a qualitative focus on employing diverse teaching strategies to enhance learning experiences for a diverse student body, emphasizing a commitment to inclusive education that prioritizes equity and inclusion. Hence, quantitative and qualitative results merges.

Similarly, in the quantitative findings under the indicators communication item encouraging students to respect each other and their opinions and indicator learning item acting as the resource person, working to support and enhance students learning which all are rated as very high, which means that participants always manifested these results. The findings are connected to the qualitative findings categorize as recognition of student diversity under the core idea understanding the diversity of each student in the classroom. Therefore, high ratings for encouraging respect among students, valuing student voices, and providing supportive learning resources, along with a qualitative emphasis on understanding the diversity of each student, demonstrate a commitment to cultivating an optimal learning environment that recognizes and accommodates student diversity, enhancing pedagogy. Hence, quantitative and qualitative findings merges.

Furthermore, in the quantitative findings under the indicator impact specifically items, utilizing alternative approaches to learning to encourage the class and requiring personally meaningful task that hold personal significance towards my students which are all rated as very high. This means that these results are always manifested by the respondents. The results are connected to the qualitative findings categorize as understanding students' needs and preferences under the core idea having difficulties in catering individual needs through not knowing the students' learning styles and preferences. This means that the high ratings for utilizing alternative learning approaches and incorporating personally meaningful tasks for students, along with a qualitative focus on understanding students' needs and preferences, demonstrate a commitment to equity and inclusion by addressing individual learning styles and preferences to enhance educational outcomes. Hence, quantitative and qualitative results merges.

In addition, in the quantitative findings under the indicator competence items possessing the necessary skills to empower learners and studying the lesson before having my session in class, are rated as very high by the participants. The results is connected to the qualitative findings categorize as improvement of teaching-learning process under the core idea identifying applicable strategies and approaches to cater the diverse students inside the classroom. This means that the high ratings for possessing necessary skills to empower learners and studying lessons before class sessions, combined with a qualitative focus on improving the teaching-learning process through applicable strategies to cater to diverse students, highlight a commitment to enhancing pedagogy by recognizing and accommodating student diversity. Therefore, quantitative and qualitative results merges.

Insights of the Board Program Instructors with regards in implementing Differentiated Instruction and Learner Empowerment

In the quantitative phase under the indicator content item, utilizing solid grasp of the subject matter content inherent in the lesson and under the indicator procedure item, instructing my students to take notes when I am lecturing which are all rated very high which means, participant is always manifested with these results. The findings are connected to the qualitative result categorize as under the core idea importance of having differentiated instruction to empower learners in the classroom. Hence, the high ratings for utilizing a solid grasp of subject matter content, along with a qualitative focus on differentiated instruction and personalized learning, converge to emphasize the importance of employing differentiated instruction to empower learners in the classroom and foster academic success. Thus, quantitative and qualitative results merges.

Moreover, in the quantitative phase under the category communication items about using differentiated instruction in my lessons' activities and encouraging students to respect each other and their opinion which are all rated very high means respondents always manifested these results. The results are connected to the qualitative findings categorize as creative supportive learning environment under core idea about fostering a comfortable learning environment towards the students' learning experience. This means that the convergence of high ratings for using differentiated instruction and promoting respect among students, along with a qualitative focus on fostering a comfortable learning environment, underscores the importance of creating a supportive atmosphere to enhance students' learning experiences and promote optimal learning environments for student success. Thus, quantitative and qualitative results merges.

Similarly, in the quantitative phase under the category impact items, choosing the methods I can use to perform my work and making an impact on the way things run in my class, are all rated as very high. The results are connected to the qualitative findings categorize as classroom management and instructional leadership under the core idea having the authority to facilitate the learners' learning. This means that the high ratings for effective method selection and impactful classroom presence, coupled with a qualitative emphasis on instructional leadership, underscore the importance of possessing the authority to facilitate student learning effectively through classroom management practices that promote student engagement. This results both quantitative and qualitative, merges.

Furthermore, in the quantitative findings under the indicator meaningfulness item, considering the task I have required in my class to be valuable to my students and under the indicator competence item, building confidence in my ability to successfully perform the task

in the class which are rated as very high, which means that this result is always manifested by the participants. The results is connected to the qualitative findings categorize as creative supportive learning environment under the core idea, fostering a comfortable learning environment towards the students' learning experience. Therefore, the high ratings for valuing tasks and building confidence, combined with a focus on fostering a supportive and creative learning environment, underscore the critical importance of such approaches in enhancing student success. This result both quantitative and qualitative, merges.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

First, the status of differentiated instruction is very high in terms of lesson design and implementation, content, procedure, communication, and learning. And the status of learner empowerment is also very high in terms of impact, meaningfulness, and competence. Hence, this indicate that the indicators of differentiated instruction and learner empowerment among the faculty of KCAST board programs are always manifested by instructors under the board programs.

Second, the findings revealed the significant relationship of differentiated instruction and learner empowerment among the faculty of KCAST board programs using Mean, Standard Deviation and Pearson r . It was revealed that there is significant relationship between differentiated instruction and learner empowerment.

Third, the thematic analysis of the qualitative data was done based from the responses gained through the conduct of in-depth interview (IDI). The results gave more information about the side of the in terms of their experiences and strategies of the board program instructors in terms of implementing differentiated instruction and learner empowerment. Qualitatively, instructors under the faculty of KCAST board programs have been experiencing different situations which contribute to the way various factors affect their strategies and approaches in implementing differentiated instruction and learner empowerment. The following themes were emerged: recognition and accommodation of student diversity to enhance pedagogy, equity and inclusion in education, effective time management in education, collaborative learning for inclusive engagement, and harmonizing academic standards and students' diverse needs.

Fifth, from the participants responses, other themes are identified which show the insights shared of board program instructors with regards to the implementation of differentiated instruction and learner empowerment. The following are the themes: fostering academic success thru personalized learning and differentiated instruction, cultivation of optimal learning environment for student success, effective teaching practices for student engagement, collaborative professional growth for effective teaching and lifelong learning and professional growth in education.

Lastly, to better understand the relationship between differentiated instruction and learner empowerment, the responses were analyzed thematically to confirm the quantitative results of the study. Both the findings from the two phases are integrated based on the nature plan. The status of differentiated instruction and learner empowerment among the faculty of KCAST board programs based on the quantitative results show that it converged to the data gained from the qualitative phase. Both of the quantitative and qualitative results confirms that there is a significant relationship between differentiated instruction and learner empowerment.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendation were being drawn:

To enhance the study exploring the relationship between differentiated instruction and learner empowerment among the faculty of KCAST board programs, the researcher recommend broadening the scope of the research by including a diverse range of participants beyond the current specific respondents. This may involve incorporating feedback from students and instructors across all programs in KCAST. Additionally, employing mixed methods such as qualitative interviews alongside quantitative surveys could provide a more comprehensive understanding of how differentiated instruction impacts learner empowerment. This approach would allow for richer data collection and analysis, leading to more robust conclusions.

Since the status of differentiated instruction reveals that among the five indicators of differentiated instruction, the procedures have the lowest mean which affects how instructors implement differentiated instruction in the classroom. To address this, it is recommended that educators focus on enhancing the clarity and effectiveness of instructional procedures by providing clear guidelines and training on how to implement differentiated instruction strategies. Additionally, fostering a supportive classroom culture that encourages collaboration and flexibility in teaching methods can help teachers better adapt their practices to meet the diverse needs of students. By prioritizing professional development in this area and promoting a student-centered approach, educators can improve the successful implementation of differentiated instruction to maximize learning outcomes for all students.

Similarly, since the status of learner empowerment reveals that among the three indicators of learner empowerment, impact and meaningfulness have the lowest mean which affect how diverse students are being empowered inside the classroom setting. It is recommended that, to improve the learner empowerment of diverse students in the classroom setting, it is recommended to design service-learning experiences that provide meaningful tasks to choose from, opportunities to develop competence, and a chance to make an impact. The instructor can also foster learner empowerment by creating a learning environment where the coursework is perceived as relevant, and there are opportunities for students to make choices and receive feedback on their progress.

Moreover, based from the qualitative phase results in the lived experiences of the board program instructors with regards to effectively

implement differentiated instruction and learner empowerment, it is recommended that instructors create a supportive learning environment that fosters student autonomy and ownership over their learning experiences. This can be achieved by setting up individual meetings with students to explain the concept of student empowerment and how to target their needs with specific practice, and guiding students to set measurable and attainable goals. Lastly, it is important for institutions to establish and support centers for teaching and learning to provide consistent training in teaching innovation for all faculty, making inclusive teaching central to faculty roles. By incorporating these strategies and initiatives, instructors can better support diverse students and create an inclusive, empowering, and critical thinking learning environment. To address and cater to the diverse learning needs of students, it is recommended that educators implement differentiated instruction and foster learner empowerment in their classrooms. Teachers should be encouraged to participate in professional development opportunities to enhance their understanding and implementation of differentiated instruction. Additionally, institutions should establish guidelines and policies that support differentiated instruction and learner empowerment, and provide resources and support for teachers to implement these strategies effectively.

Lastly, to promote differentiated instruction and learner empowerment, the researcher recommends the implementation of a student-centered learning approach that allows for personalized learning experiences. This could include the use of technology tools such as adaptive learning platforms, which can adjust to a learner's needs and pace. Additionally, providing students with choices in how they learn and demonstrate their understanding, such as through project-based learning or alternative assessments, can help to empower them and foster a sense of ownership over their learning. Furthermore, promoting a growth mindset and encouraging students to take ownership of their learning through self-assessment and goal-setting can help to empower them and promote a lifelong love of learning.

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